

THE RICO Act and THE MAGNITSKY Act - The Only Decision Against the Fight Against the Judges of the Mafia and the MAFIA IN THE COURT in Bulgaria , Supported by the European Commission - Claims to The EC and Bulgaria for 325 Billion Euros From US and other Companies

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ABSTRACT: Lord prof PhD Momtchil Dobrev-Halachev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-DObreva developed 2006 "Theory of degree of democracy" and "Theory of degree of justice / injustice /" based on their practice in court, prosecutor's office, state. Prof. Momchil Dobrev has been creating Theory of Corruption, "Theory of the Mafia," Theory of Mafia ", " Financial Banking Resource Technological Mafia Materialism "since 2003"

KEY WORDS: Magnitsky act, RICO act, mafia, corruption, theory, finance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lord Prof. PhD Momtchil Dobrev-Halachev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev developed 2006 "Theory of degree of democracy" and "Theory of degree of justice" based on their practice in court, prosecution, state and especially the practice of Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev as a judge for decades experience as such as a civil and criminal judge and Prof. Momchil Dobrev participated as an observer in various types of elections. .

In the year 2001 Lord Prof. Momtchil DObrev developed the Theory of the mafia and Theory of corruption. All the both theories has been developed by analyzing the mafia and the corruption all over the wprld. In Bulgaria, germany, European Union, and other countires.

In the year 2010 Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed the 'Theory of Mafiotismus' as a new type of government oriented only in the private interests of individuals and private institutions.

The fight against the mafia and corruption in Bulgaria and in the European Commission and especially in the court and the prosecutor's office is huge, as the prosecutor's office and the court are used by the mafia to steal property, factories, repression, coercion, extortion of honest citizens.

In the article we describe one such case, which is striking and proves the huge tentacles of the mafia in court and prosecutor's office in Bulgaria used for theft and racketeering and coercion.

1.1 Introduce the Problem

The problem with the mafia and corruption in the court and prosecutor's office in Bulgaria is huge. Through the court and prosecutor's office, the mafia in Bulgaria represses citizens and companies, steals property, steals factories for tens of millions of euros, the court legalizes theft of property, factories, prosecution is used for repression and pressure, and coercion and extortion to steal property, factories .

Although the European Commission and the European Union are constantly informed about this mafia in court, prosecutor's office, state that the country is run by the mafia, the European Commission and the Union do not take any measures or action.

They obviously have an interest in that.

We have repeatedly applied evidence of the scale of this mafia. The basis of this mafia and corruption in Bulgaria and the European Union and the European Commission, Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev, established in 2001. Mafia Theory and Corruption Theory with all its manifestations. Based on these theories, Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev also defines the formula of the mafia, the

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formula of corruption. Based on these processes, Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev also created the Theory and Practice of Mafitiism, defining a formula of mafia, how it works, how it is organized, in whose interests it works at its expense.

Corruption and the mafia in a country destroy democracy, freedoms, human rights, the rule of law. As a result Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Lady Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev also created "Theory of the Degree of Democracy" and "Theory of the Degree of Justice / Injustice" as well as "Theory of Socio-Humanism" - a society that excludes the shortcomings of neoliberalism, globalism, wild market economy, and creates the foundations of a NEW HUMAN SOCIETY based on completely different principles, as well as economic and social, managerial and others.

As a result of the struggle of Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev against corruption and the mafia in Bulgaria and the European Union and the European Commission since 2011. Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev experienced 9 / nine / attempts to kill him and his relatives.

As a result and the only solution for the fight against corruption, Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev sees only the application of the MAGNETIC act and the RICO act in the fight against this corruption and mafia in Bulgaria and in the European Union and the European Commission.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

Research methods of analysis, verification, control of all factors in corruption and the mafia that affect a society for its viability, the degree of democracy in that society, laws, their implementation by judges, prosecutors, statesmen, ministers, minister - Chairs, state and municipal officials and others.

- Analysis of the laws of a country and the European Commission.
- Analysis of all authorities in a country - judicial, legislative, executive and the European Union and the European Commission
- Analysis of the implementation of the laws of a country and the European Commission
- Analysis of governance in a country and a society and the European Commission
- Analysis of public resource management in a country and the European Commission
- Analysis of the existence of corruption and mafia in the judiciary, in the state system and in the European Union.
- Analysis of the work of the prosecutor's office as a guarantor of the existence and development of mafia and the rule of law in a society.
- Analysis of the judiciary - laws, judges, selection of judges, development of judges, violations of judges, disciplinary and other liability of judges, prosecutors, investigators, guarantors of democratization in a society

3. The Magnitsky Act and the RICO Act - the only decision for the fight against corruption and the mafia at the state level in Bulgaria and the European Commission

The formulas of mafia, the formula of the corruption, formula of degree of democracy, formula of degree of justice, formula of mafiotismus

3.1. The Magnitsky act and the RICO act

THE RICO act

The **Racketeer Influenced and Corrupt Organizations (RICO) Act** is a United States federal law that provides for extended criminal penalties and a civil cause of action for acts performed as part of an ongoing criminal organization.

The RICO Act focuses specifically on racketeering and allows the leaders of a syndicate to be tried for the crimes they ordered others to do or assisted them in doing, closing a perceived loophole.

For example, before RICO, a person who instructed someone else to murder could be exempt from prosecution because they did not personally commit the crime.

RICO was enacted by section 901(a) of the Organized Crime Control Act of 1970 (Pub.L. 91-452, 84 Stat. 922, enacted October 15, 1970) and is codified at 18 U.S.C. ch. 96 as 18 U.S.C. §§ 1961-1968. G. Robert Blakey, an adviser to the United States Senate Government Operations Committee, drafted the law under the close supervision of the committee's chairman, Senator John Little McClellan. It was enacted as Title IX of the Organized Crime Control Act of 1970, and signed into law by US President Richard M. Nixon.

While its original use in the 1970s was to prosecute the Mafia as well as others who were actively engaged in organized crime, its later application has been more widespread.

Beginning in 1972, 33 states adopted state RICO laws to be able to prosecute similar conduct.

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Under RICO, a person who has committed "at least two acts of racketeering activity" drawn from a list of 35 crimes— 27 federal crimes and 8 state crimes—within a 10-year period can be charged with racketeering if such acts are related in one of four specified ways to an "enterprise." Those found guilty of racketeering can be fined up to \$25,000 and sentenced to 20 years in prison per racketeering count.^[3] In addition, the racketeer must forfeit all ill-gotten gains and interest in any business gained through a pattern of "racketeering activity."

In many cases, the threat of a RICO indictment can force defendants to plead guilty to lesser charges, in part because the seizure of assets would make it difficult to pay a defense attorney. Despite its harsh provisions, a RICO-related charge is considered easy to prove in court since it focuses on patterns of behavior as opposed to criminal acts.

When the U.S. Attorney decides to indict someone under RICO, they have the option of seeking a pre-trial restraining order or injunction to temporarily seize a defendant's assets and prevent the transfer of potentially forfeitable property, as well as require the defendant to put up a performance bond. This provision was placed in the law because the owners of Mafia-related shell corporations often absconded with the assets. An injunction or performance bond ensures that there is something to seize in the event of a guilty verdict.

RICO also permits a private individual "damaged in his business or property" by a "racketeer" to file a civil suit. The plaintiff must prove the existence of an "enterprise." The defendant(s) are not the enterprise; in other words, the defendant(s) and the enterprise are not one and the same.^[6] There must be one of four specified relationships between the defendant(s) and the enterprise: either the defendant(s) invested the proceeds of the pattern of racketeering activity into the enterprise (18 U.S.C. § 1962(a)); or the defendant(s) acquired or maintained an interest in, or control of, the enterprise through the pattern of racketeering activity (subsection (b)); or the defendant(s) conducted or participated in the affairs of the enterprise "through" the pattern of racketeering activity (subsection (c)); or the defendant(s) conspired to do one of the above (subsection (d)).^[7] In essence, the enterprise is either the 'prize,' 'instrument,' 'victim,' or 'perpetrator' of the racketeers.^[8] A civil RICO action can be filed in state or federal court.^[9]

Both the criminal and civil components allow the recovery of treble damages (damages in triple the amount of actual/compensatory damages).

Magnitsky act

The Magnitsky Act fights corruption on a global scale, in defense of human rights. The Magnitsky Act fights against every corruption and mafia in a country, against corrupt practices at every level in a country, against corrupt practices. The Magnitsky Act is an opportunity to fight the oligarchy in one country, to fight the mafia in one country, the mafia at any level in one country. The Magnitsky Act became law on December 14, 2012 during the presidency of President Barack Obama.

The implementation of the Magnitsky Act by the United States occurs when the United States decides to intervene in corruption schemes in a country, its practices, schemes, restrictions on human rights, in order to restore the rule of law.

At the moment, the fight is between crime and the rule of law. When crime has reached its peak, corruption schemes, mafia practices rule in a society, and thus destroy democracy, justice, the rule of law.

The scope of the Magnitsky Act allows the United States to impose sanctions on politicians, government officials, their assistants, and administrations that violate human rights and engage in widespread corruption. The consequences are sanctions, blocking of assets, bank accounts of the sanctioned persons and their relatives of assets around the world, freezing of assets, bank accounts, blocking of transactions, international transfers in dollars.

3.2./ THE MAFIA IN THE COURT IN BULGARIA and The inaction and support of this mafia by the EUROPEAN COMMISSION and the EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT

BULGARIA - THE MAFIA HAS A COURT

We will not go into details and therefore we will pay attention to what is the reason for the current state of our country.

In our homeland: Corruption has become the norm. The mafia has become the norm.

Corruption and the mafia in the court and among judges in Bulgaria has become the norm.

The court is used for legalized theft of property and factories for tens of millions of euros, the court is used for repression, racketeering, coercion of extortion of companies and citizens to donate and transfer property, companies, factories in favor of the mafia.

The mafia in court is not worried about committing crimes and lawlessness.

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The Prosecutor's Office with Chief Prosecutors SOTIR TSATSAROV, PROF. BORIS VELCHEV, IVAN GESHEV is used for repression and racketeering and coercion of honest citizens and companies to transfer businesses, properties for HUNDREDS OF MILLIONS EURO to people and companies of the mafia AS WELL AS LEGALIZING A CRIMINAL

At the same time, the PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE ACTS and COVERS CRIMES committed by JUDGES, prime ministers, ministers, statesmen, civil servants.

The mafia in its country appoints the members of the Supreme Judicial Council, which conceals, obviously proven crimes of judges, legalizes a crime committed by judges, does not act in case of proven crimes of judges.

The norm is for the Supreme Judicial Council to cover up offenses committed by judges, lawlessness of judges, repression by judges, legalization of theft of equipment, factories, property for hundreds of millions of euros.

It is NORMAL for the prosecution not to bring charges against JUDGES

On the other hand, the SJC amends laws, changes laws and carries out REPRESSIONS AGAINST PERSONS FIGHTING AGAINST THIS MAFIAV

BY ORDER OF THE MAFIA AND THE MAFIA IN COURT AND THE SUPREME JUDICIAL COUNCIL AND PRIME MINISTER BOYKO BORISOV, CITIZENS WHO ARE FIGHTING AGAINST THIS MAFIA AND THE CRIMES ARE JUDGED BY THE COURT OF JUDGES.

NORMA is for prosecutors not to bring charges of theft of land from private lands, with which the North Tangent was built, the theft of slot machines by former judge Yordanka Mollova and her brother Hristo Mollov, the violations of PEA Dichev, the theft for zero pennies of properties for over 500 million euros from EMIL KYULEV and his heirs and from DONEV, thefts of factories, the lawlessness of judges Valkov, Raina Martinova, Albena Boteva, Desislava Yordanova, Nelly Kutzkova, Eric Vassilev and hundreds of other judges from SRS, SCC SAS, VKSy BOS, KOS, VROS and other courts.

It is the norm for prosecutors from the specialized prosecutor's office to cover up clearly proven crimes committed by judges, legalizing theft of property for hundreds of millions, legalizing theft of property, legalizing theft of equipment for tens of millions, legalizing theft of entire factories, and legalizing open and proven crimes. Judges, from metropolitan mayors and others?!?!?!?

NORMA is for prosecutors to delay pre-trial proceedings for years against people supported by the mafia, with the ultimate goal of passing the statute of limitations.

It is NORM for prosecutors to violate the laws of our country with the ultimate goal of fulfilling the order - TIGHTENING ZADAR over a person close to the mafia, an official, a minister, a prime minister, and others.

NORMA is for prosecutors to BRING ACCUSATIONS against appointed people, critics of the mafia and people of the mafia, who are in violation of the law with the ultimate goal of racketeering, coercion, RUIN OF HUMAN LIVES, FATE, deterioration of health.

NORM is that prosecutors do not respect the laws when it comes to people close to the mafia.

It is the norm for prosecutors, in case of indisputable evidence, graphological expertise for fraud on a particularly large scale, to delay investigations in order to pass the statute of limitations against the perpetrators, who boast that they pay prosecutors so as not to bring charges against them.

It is the norm for mafia judges to confirm these terminations by prosecutors despite indisputable evidence. / example Metodi Lalov /

It is the norm for judges to place orders for the mafia and to issue decisions that legalize the theft of private property in favor of the Sofia Municipality - the GERB representatives.

It is the norm for judges to place orders for the mafia and to legalize thefts of factories, equipment worth tens of millions of euros, theft of property for the benefit of third parties.

NORMA is for judges to terminate cases against banks, insurance companies, state institutions, ministries, the National Revenue Agency, the Ministry of Interior in execution of an order of the executive branch and of mafia companies.

NORM is to disappear lawsuits filed against Banks for stolen money - hundreds of thousands of leva, millions of leva, for damages - losses of billions.

NORM is to disappear lawsuits against state companies, state institutions for proven damages, losses, crimes.

THE NORM is to LEGISLATE CRIMINALS COMMITTED BY THE EXECUTIVE POWER WITH DECISIONS OF JUDGES.

It is the norm for judges to make absurd decisions by violating the laws, not recognizing the laws, with the ultimate goal of repressing the plaintiffs in order to lose money - tens - millions of leva, TO MAKE THE ORDER OF THE MAFIA.

It is the norm for prosecutors not to bring charges against judges who have violated the Penal Code and the laws, because these judges serve the mafia.

LEGALIZATION OF RACKETS IS THE NORM.

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Racketeering and coercion by the NRA IS THE NORM - IN VIOLATION AND NON-ENFORCEMENT OF JUDGMENTS ENTERED INTO FORCE.

RACKET AND FORCE FROM THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE IS THE NORM.

THE LEGALIZATION OF EXTORTION and coercion by prosecutors and judges is NORM.

INJUSTICE is the NORM.

THE LEGISLATION by judges and prosecutors is NORM.

THE IMPUNITY OF PROSECUTORS AND JUDGES IS NORM.

THE LAWLESSNESS of prosecutors and judges IS THE NORM.

NON-COMPLIANCE OF THE LAW by judges and prosecutors is a NORM.

VIOLATION OF THE LAW by prosecutors and judges NORM.

THE NORM is THE THEFT OF BUSINESS by people from the mafia through prosecutors and judges.

THE NORM is THE THEFT OF PROPERTY by people from the mafia through prosecutors and judges.

THE NORM IS THAT THERE IS NO JUSTICE, THERE IS NO JUSTICE.

THE NORM IS THE INACTION OF THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION AND THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT despite the application of evidence of the mafia in a country, the mafia in court, the mafia in the prosecution, the mafia in the government of Bulgaria.

Bulgaria is used only for money laundering, 30 to 50 percent of all investments in equipment, machinery, investments are returned to the company of EUROPE and Western countries.

It is the norm for judges and prosecutors not to comply with the laws, to violate laws, not to obey laws, not to apply laws, to deliberately wrongly treat laws, rights, freedoms, evidence.

NORMA is for judges to legalize the theft of a private property in favor of Sofia Municipality with Mayor Fandakova in gross violation of the laws of this country with the ultimate goal of losing a private person to his inherited property in downtown Sofia - worth more than 3.5 million euros due to its investment value.

NORM is JUDGES to legalize theft of equipment, machinery and equipment for millions of levs

THE NORM is FOR JUDGES IN THE SERVICE OF THE MAFIA to legalize the theft of an entire factory and cause a loss of the owner with a share - shares of over 41% - losses of over 100 million euros.

NORM IS JUDGES to legalize the theft of property for zero pennies and is "donated to a person by a drug gang.

The judges of the Supreme Court of Cassation, of the Sofia Court of Appeal, of the Burgas Court of Appeal, of the Plovdiv Court of Appeal, of the Varna Court of Appeal, of all the district and district courts of the Sofia City Court, of the Court COMPLY WITH, IMPLEMENT, FOLLOW THE LAWS OF THIS COUNTRY.

It has become the norm for the prosecutor's office to bring fabricated charges against dissidents and against fighters against the mafia and corruption in court.

The norm is for the prosecutors of Filchev, Assoc. Prof. Boris Velchev, Tsatsarov and Geshev not to bring charges against JUDGES WHO LEGALIZE the theft of property by the oligarchs Emil Kyulev, Donev - property that belongs to the heirs of insurance companies.

It is the norm for the prosecutors of TSATSAROV and GESHEV and for them personally not to bring charges for the theft of land over 2.9 million cubic meters of land from private land, with which the NORTH TANGENT of the city of Sofia was built.

IT IS NORM FOR JUDGES TO TERMINATE CASES against BANKS, insurance companies, against Sofia Municipality and other municipalities, against state bodies, against the lawlessness of the Ministry of Interior, the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, the Ministry of Energy and the Ministry of Economy.

THE NORM IS TO DISAPPEAR CASES filed against BANKS, Insurance companies,

THE NORM IS TO DISAPPEAR filed lawsuits for PROPERTY OF HONEST CITIZENS stolen by OLIGARCHES AND MAFIOTS for 2 BILLION EUROS.

THE NORM IS TO DELAY TEN - 15 YEARS OF CASES INTENTIONALLY SUBMITTED BY MAFIA COMPANIES FOR PROPERTY, OWNED BY PRIVATE PERSONS, e; with the ultimate goal TO BE ROBBED.

THE NORM IS FOR THE COURT TO SERVICE THE MAFIA in delaying the property cases of honest citizens and companies, because the MAFIA LIKED THESE PROPERTIES.

NORM is from 2008. not to be ACCUSED against PEA Dichev, PEA Yakimov, PEA. Cholakov and dozens of other PEAs violated the law.

NORMA is the double standard in the prosecution.

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LEGALIZATION OF RACKETS IS THE NORM.

Provided that there is evidence of ownership of property with equity participation, effective court decision, actually proven ownership, the judges LEGALIZE THEFT OF PROPERTY in favor of Sofia Municipality - INACTION OF PROSECUTORS NAVA FILCHEV. B. VELCHEV, TO TSATSAROV AND TO IVAN GESHEV.

-How to legalize the theft of property from the CITY MUNICIPALITY through a decision of judges on property, which according to the restitution must be returned to the heirs - losses of millions. - INACTION OF THE PROSECUTORS OF TSATSAROV AND GESHEV BY A SPECIALIZED PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE.

3.3./ INJUSTICE DEGREE FORMULA, DEMOCRACY DEGREE FORMULA, Formula of Corruption, Formula of Mafia, Formula of MAFIOTISMUS, Formula of Dgerre of Trust.

FORMULA of Degree of Justice / Injustice - 2006 - Prof. Momchil Dobrev and Prof. Mariola Garibova-Dobrev /:

JUSTICE / INJUSTICE = POWER + Influence + Relationships + Interests + MONEY / AND + Mafia structure / internal or external / + Monopoly rights / rights + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility to make an alternative decision - Obligation - Responsibility - morality ethics - observance / application / implementation of the law by judges / prosecutors / statesmen - Control / Sanctions - Corruption - Mafiaization - TRUST / DEGREE OF TRUST.

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FORMULA of DEGREE OF DEMOCRACY / 2006

DEMOCRACY = POWER - Influence - Relationships - Interests - ORDER / AND - Mafia / mafia structure / internal or external / - Monopoly rights + laws / rules / practices / procedures // freedoms // - possibility to make an alternative decision - Obligation - Responsibility - morality / ethics - observance / application / enforcement of the law by judges / prosecutors / statesmen - Control / Sanction - corruption / corrupt practices - information - manipulation - society structure - economy - inequality + obligations - Justice / injustice - Trust / Degree of trust

CORRUPTION FORMULA / 2001 - Theory of Corruption - Prof. Momchil Dobrev

Corruption = Monopoly rights / rights + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility to make an alternative decision - obligation - responsibility - morality / ethics.

MAFIA FORMULA - 2001 - Mafia Theory - Prof. Momchil Dobrev

MAFIA = Power + Influence + Relationships + Interests + ORDER / And + Mafia structure / internal or external structure / + Monopoly rights / rights + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility to make an alternative decision - obligation - responsibility - morality / ethics.

FORMULA OF MAFIOTISM - 2001 - Theory of Mafiaism - Prof. Momchil Dobrev

MAFIOTISMUS = PERSONAL Power / on the top of the state institutions / state and etc./ + Influence + Connections / to personal, private companies + Interests / personal, private, corporative / + ORDER / ORDERS + Personal Management of all state neaveus + Personal Control of all state niveausMafia structure / inside of or outside / + Monopoly Riegths + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility of taking an alternative decision - obligation - responsibilities - morality / ethics + Personal management and personal control of Distribution of public state monetary and another resource.

4. SPECIFIC EXAMPLES OF LAWLESSNESS, JUDGES 'MAFIA, JUDICIAL CASES, EVIDENCE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM IN BULGARIA

4.1./ JUDGES WHO HAVE REJECTED HUNDREDS of citizens and companies do not GIVE REJECTIONS IN CASES THAT THE SAME INDIVIDUALS AND COMPANIES MUST LOSE THEM. THEY REFUSED TO REMOVE AND DECIDED DECISIONS THAT LEGALIZE the theft of property, equipment, machinery, factories for tens of millions of euros. CRIMINAL LAWLESSNESS, DOUBLE STANDARD, REPRESSION, COORDINATION?!?!

Judge RAINA MARTINOVA in civil case 8310/2015 according to the list of the Sofia City Court USES HIS OFFICIAL POSITION FOR REPRESSION, on chgrd. 332/2019, and the judges of the Supreme Court of Cassation Svetla TSACHEVA, ALEXANDER TSONEV and PHILIP VLADIMIROV on chgrd. 2408/2019. They LEGALIZE THE REPRESSION of the natural person, provided that they have recused themselves in the cases of the same natural person.

Judge Raina Martinova from the Sofia City Court how in case 8310/2015 on the list of the Sofia City Court with ruling № 28155 dated 05.12.2018. :

- HEM LEAVE WITHOUT RESPECTED MY REQUEST FOR HER WITHDRAWAL
- HEM RELEASES MD FROM PAYMENT OF THE STATE FEE OF 10000 / TEN THOUSAND / BGN,
- HEM INSTRUCTS THE MD TO PRESENT PROOF OF PAYMENT OF STATE FEE IN FAVOR OF SCC IN THE AMOUNT OF 10,000 / TEN THOUSAND / - IN CASE OF COMPLETED AND COMPLETED FULL.
- HEM LEAVES MD'S REQUEST FOR AMENDMENT OF THE CLAIM WITHOUT RESPECT - for reduced is under BGN 10,000
- HEM RETURNS MY REQUEST.

le MD in case the case is terminated, the returned claim is SENTENCED TO PAY TO THE SCC THE AMOUNT OF BGN 10,000 / TEN THOUSAND /.

And the scheme of the MAFIA in the higher instance is confirmed to confirm the definition, the order of the previous instance.

Judges Vladimir Grigorov Valkov, Alexander Emilov Angelov and Jr. Judge Svetoslav Tihomirov Spasenov of the Sofia City Court ruled in court. 11664/2013 dated 17.05.2019 for amounts of EUR 1250 each, and the actual claims are partial and are for the amounts of EUR 57640, which practically deliberately interrupts and terminates the rights of the affected person to appeal the decision of the judges of the Sofia City Court before Supreme Court of Cassation and it is a question of LEGALIZATION OF

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THEFT OF EQUIPMENT confirmed by the National Revenue Agency and the Prosecutor's Office. Moreover, Judges Vladimir Valkov and Alexander Angelov recused themselves in other cases of the individual.

- Losses of 48,582 euros with the corresponding interest from 2009. over 195 percent,
- Lost benefits and profits of over EUR 1,350,000 / one million three hundred and fifty euros.

Judges Vladimir VALKOV, Judge ELITSA YORDANOVA and Judge RAYNA MARTINOVA of the Sofia City Court under Vgrd. 82/2010 - Go - 2 - instead of a partial claim in the amount of 1525 euros, they issue a decision for the amount of 900 euros with a decision of 08.07.2019. Ie there was no such claim for 900 euros, but 1525 euros, and a SUPERPETITUM is pronounced - ie. make a decision deliberately not on the claims and articles of the CPA.

Judge VLADIMIR VALKOV, ALEXANDER EMILOV ANGELOV and Jr. Judge SVETLANA ATANASOVA of the Sofia City Court in V.G. case 792/2009 - 1 GO - 2 - „B“ panel, and EUR 23,312 and respectively two of EUR 18,312 each - UNFOUNDED ENRICHMENT, and there is no REAL REALIZATION ON THESE CLAIMS, they render their decision and cite claims of EUR 2135 and EUR 2160, with and REJECTS OBSERVE APPEALS BEFORE THE SUPREME COURT OF CASSATION. LOSSES FOR OVER 16 MILLION EUROS.

The obvious is the misunderstanding and non-fulfillment of the law by judges Enchev - SCC, Evgeni Georgiev, Vladimir Kanev from SRS, Judge Vladimir Valkov, Judge Veneta Georgieva, Judge Madjarov, Judge Evtimov and dozens of judges from the marriage panel of SRS; Judge Pavkov of the Supreme Court of Cassation, Judge Vlahod of the SRS, in a case under the Domestic Population Act, for mental harassment by Sofia City Court Judge Yordanak Borisova Mollovoya, who for decades refused to comply with the contact regime and refused to see her son. to the father of his son. This is the implementation of the terms of the Criminal Code, but there is full illegal support of the above judges to non-compliance with the law and non-compliance with a court decision by Judge YORDANKA BORISOVA MOLLOVA. This is evidence of the mafia and lawlessness in the judiciary imposed by the judges The friendly contacts of the judges with the guilty judge Mollova from the Sofia City Court are above the LAW, which is already a mafia.

WHEN JUDGES REJECT ON THE CASES OF AN INDIVIDUAL AND COMPANIES REPRESENTED BY HIM AND WHEN CONSCIOUSLY DO NOT REJECT ON THE CASES WHICH THE INDIVIDUAL SHOULD LOSE ON ORDER OF THE MAFIA. Deliberately, the judge, instead of recusing himself, REFUSES TO WITHDRAW himself and MAKES A DECISION rejecting the claims and CAUSING LOSSES of tens of millions of euros.

EXAMPLE OF JUDGE VLADIMIR VALKOV of the Sofia City Court

JUDGE VLADIMIR GRIGOROV VALKOV, DESPITE THAT THE SAME JUDGE HAS MADE HIMSELF WITHDRAWN HIMSELF IN THE FOLLOWING CASES OF MD - example: CITY CASES IN SCC CITY CASE 648/2011, 528/2011, GR.D. 517/2011, GR.D. 3477/2011, GR.D. 3476/2011, GR.D. 3231/2011, GR.D. 5352/2011, GR.D. 13869/2010, GR.D. 14843/2010, GR.D. 2218/2011, GR.D. 2219/2011, GR.DELO 2217/2011, GRD. 925/2011, GR.D. 926/2011, 14407/2016 in a case against SiBANK, civil case 14404/2016 in a case against the BNB, civil case `14401/2016 against SiBANK AD and dozens of other cases LEAD BY MD and companies represented by it, the SAME using his official position, REFUSES TO REMOVE IN CASES WHICH DOMCHEV DOBREV AND THE COMPANIES REPRESENTED BY HIM MUST LOSE IN FULFILLED ON THE ORDER OF THE MAFIA FOR WHICH I WAS.

And terminates the bankruptcy case for caused losses of 460 million euros to a company close to the mafia and EVEN FINE the individual without having a court hearing twice for 150 euros, FOR NOTHING

- Terminates the bankruptcy case against a company-debtor of a natural person, who owes him 900,000 euros without interest, despite all fees paid, and fines the natural person with a fine of 150 euros without a single court hearing-
- Rules a decision in a case for "stolen equipment", proven by the prosecutor of the National Revenue Agency and confirmed by the defendant that she took this equipment and even it is still at the moment and has been used by her since 1996. in its service
- losses of over 1.4 million euros
- Decides a decision in a case in which a company that does not own two presses for the production of tiles worth more than 4 million German marks, pledges it against money in DSK Bank for millions of euros, caused losses for millions of lev
- Decides a decision on real "stolen and unpaid to a company of one person - his company equipment for two restaurants for hundreds of thousands of euros
- Resigns dozens of rulings confirming terminated cases in the RCC of a particular individual and companies represented by him.

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Example Judge Alexander Emilov Angelov

Who has reprimanded dozens of times in cases led by MD and companies represented by him when he was a junior judge in the Sofia City Court, and when he returned as a judge in the SRS - TERMINATES the cases of Momchil Dobrev, and as a judge in the Sofia City Court RULES ACTS - opposite to a decision that has already entered into force, enacts acts for legalization of theft of equipment owned by companies of Momchil Dobrev and dozens of others.

Who has given himself dozens of times REJECTIONS in cases led by MG since 2011 when he was a junior judge in the Sofia City Court, as a judge in the SRS terminates the case of MG - for a property in the center of Sofia on Maria Luiza Blvd. - on 6 floors shops, market value 4 million.

He issued an act terminating the case.

More with Resolved from 07.02.2013 Judge ALEXANDER EMILOV ANGELOV together with Judges Malin Vassilev and Genika Mihaylova legalized the theft of 50/100 id. parts of a property in the center of Sofia in FAVOR OF THE CAPITAL MUNICIPALITY. . They also own the land under them, but in reality these 50/100 id. parts are legalized in favor of the CITY MUNICIPALITY.

Judge Alexander Angelov, who, although he recused himself in the case of Mariola Garibova in 2011. as a junior judge in the Sofia City Court, issues decisions WHICH LEGALIZE THE THEFT OF INHERITANCE PROPERTY FOR RESTITUTION IN THE CENTER OF SOFIA 386 sq.m. property of Mariola Garibova in favor of the CITY MUNICIPALITY

Judge Alexander Angelov, as a judge in the SRS, terminated the case of Mariola Garibova for restoration of restitution of an entire building on Maria Luiza Blvd. on 5 floors with a shop, with attached sketch, tax assessment and paid fees, as the building was REALLY STOLEN FROM THE CAPITAL Mayor Boyko Borisov and then with Mayor FADAKOVA were issued acts of municipal property - and on condition that Judge ALEXANDER ANGELOV WAS WITHDRAWN in the case of Mariola Garibova when he was a junior judge in Sofia Euro and 5 City Court benefits and profits 350,000 euros per year

Example Judge Vladimir Stanchev Kanev

Although in the beginning of February 2020 lawsuits were filed against Judge VLADIMIR KANEV - MULTIMILLIONAIRE because he slandered, attributed crimes, accused a physical high school of crime, which did not actually commit such, he INSTEAD to withdraw his case. of this natural person, HE TERMINATES THEM.

The cases are against:

1 / . CHANNEL 3 companies, against the journalist SAMSHO DIKOV, against the journalist Margarita Mihneva, slandered two individuals in a TV show KANAL -3 and spread lies, slander, untruths about the two people in front of all Bulgarian viewers over 2.5 million.

2 / . Case against BANKER newspaper and its employees MARIETA VELINOVA, and the owner - BISDTRA GEORGIEVA and the directors Dimitar KADIYSKI and TSVETI GEROV, who in an article disseminated innocent slanderous untruths about two individuals LIES, DIRTY, FALSE THINGS, DISGUSTING LIES for honest people.

In conclusion: everyone in this failed state can WRITE lies, slander, dirt, untruth about a person, are not true, and you can not protect your honor, his dignity, his name in court because the judges SERVICEABLE mafia.

Example Judge Eric VASILEV of the Supreme Court of Cassation

Who, although he had recused himself in the case of Momchil Dobrev, issued a confirmation for termination of the case for 250,000 euros / two hundred and fifty thousand / euros for actual theft of property of the Dobrevi family through judges who "donated" this property to Dobrevi not accidentally to a person close to the private police in Burgas for ZERO HUNDREDS.

THE LOSS is over 250,000 euros

Example judges from the Supreme Court of Cassation Dragomir Dragnev, Tsonev, and dozens of others.

Example judges from SAS who recused themselves in the case of Momchil Dobrev when they were judges in the Sofia City Court, Albena Alexandrova, Sonya Naidenova, Stella Katsarova, Juliana Petkova, Aken Vodenicharov, Atansa Kemanov, Asya Sabeva, Dimitar Mirchev, Elena Tahchieva, Eliza Petrova, Zlatina Rubieva, Katerina Racheva, Ivanka Angelova, Kamelia Parvanova, Krassimir Mashev, Ristina Firipova, Maria Yanachkova, Nina Stoycheva, Nelly Kutzkova from SAS. Milen Vassilev,

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Zornitsa Haidukova, Desislava Dobрева, Galina Ivanova, Valentin Boykinov, Angelina Hristova, Anelia Tsanova, Vasil Hristakiev, Zornitsa Gladilova, Ivo Dimitrov, Dachev, Tahchieva and others.

Although Judge NELI KUTSKOVA is known throughout Bulgaria both as a judge and as a representative of the Union of Judges, that she recused herself in the case of MD, she issued a deed in a case for property paid by MD, which property MD LOSES - in the center of SOFIA. worth 250,000 euros.

The above-mentioned judges from the Supreme Administrative Court confirmed the termination of cases terminated by the judges of the Sofia City Court, although they argued in cases when they were judges in the Sofia City Court in the cases of Momchil Dobrev. They confirmed the termination of the case for millions of leva, terminated by the judges of the Kyustendil District Court, who on the other hand did not recusal themselves in the case of Momchil Dobrev. The same is confirmed by the termination of cases brought by Momchil Dobrev in the Supreme Court of Cassation, Vratsa District Court, Montana District Court, Vidin District Court, Pernik District Court.

Example Judge Gergana Nedeva - 39th panel Sofia District Court

Although Judge Gergana NEDEVA STILL ON 21.11.2019. has REJECTED on another CASE 62258/2019 SUBMITTED BY ME of SRS, with Order № 281177 dated 21.11.2019. BY WHICH JUDGE GERGANNA NEDEVA EVEN JUDGED and DEFAMATED an individual with whom she committed articles of the Penal Code.

However, her conduct is the SAME JUDGE in gross violation of any LAWS, in the EXPRESS USE OF OFFICIAL POSITION with the clear purpose of causing harm. LOSSES IN A HUGE AMOUNT, in violation of any MORAL AND ETHICAL NORMS and rules of judges in Bulgaria DECIDES its act dated 20.12.2019. in civil case 31714/2013 - 39 panel ruled Decision № 308197 WHICH REJECTS the claim against the defendants one of which is the former judge of the Sofia City Court YORDANKA BORISOVA MOLLOVA.

WHEN JUDGES FROM THE SECOND AND THIRD INSTANCE INSTITUTION EXAMPLE THE SOFIA COURT OF APPEALS AND THE SUPREME COURT OF CASSATION

In cases instituted in the Sofia Court of Appeal or the Supreme Court of Cassation, with plaintiff D and companies represented by him, respect given request and request.

THIS IS PROOF OF THE MAFIA IN COURT - the judges on behalf of the MAFIA CONFIRM THE ACTS OF THE BELOW COURT, IN PERFORMANCE OF THE ORDER.

EVERY ABSURDITY AND LAWLESSNESS IS CONFIRMED.

THE ORDER IS BEING FULFILLED.

Example of the judges from the Sofia Court of Appeal, who recused themselves in the case of D when they were judges in the Sofia City Court, Albena Alexandrova, Sonya Naidenova, Stella Katsarova, Juliana Petkova, Aken Vodenicharov, Atansa Kemanov, Asya Sabeva, Dimitar Mirchev, Elenah Tachie , Elizabeth Petrova, Zlatina Rubieva, Katerina Racheva, Ivanka Angelova, Kamelia Parvanova, Krassimir Mashev, Ristina Firipova, Maria Yanachkova, Nina Stoycheva, Nelly Kutzkova from SAS. Milen Vassilev, Zornitsa Haidukova, Desislava Dobрева, Galina Ivanova, Valentin Boykinov, Angelina Hristova, Anelia Tsanova, Vasil Hristakiev, Zornitsa Gladilova, Ivo Dimitrov, Dachev, and others and who, instead of arguing in the SAS cases, CONFIRM .

Although Judge NELI KUTSKOVA of the Sofia Court of Appeals, known throughout Bulgaria both as a judge and as a representative of the Union of Judges, for recusing herself in cases, she ruled on a case for a property paid for by MD, which MD loses - in the center of SOFIA worth EUR 250,000.

It is no coincidence that judges such as Atanas Kemanov, Asya Sabeva, Juliana Petkova, Dimitar Mirchev, Elena Tahchieva, Elizabeth Petrova, Zlatina Rubieva, Ivanka Angelova, Kamelia Pavanova, Krassimir Mashev, Katerina Racheva, Kristina Filipova, Maria Yanachkova, Nina Stoli Haidukova, Milen Vassilev, Daniela Doncheva, Zornitsa Gladilova, Vasil Hristakiev, judges from the Supreme Court of Cassation such as Erik Vassilev Dragomir Dagnev, Tsoney, who recused themselves in dozens of my cases when they were judges in the Sofia City Court in cases of private appeals against rulings against It is obvious and proven that my cases in the Sofia City Court are being deliberately terminated, these judges from the Supreme Court of Cassation and the Supreme Court of Cassation OBVIOUSLY FORGETTING THAT THEY HAVE REJECTED TENS OF MY CASES IN THE SCC, the same instead of recusing .

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The above-mentioned judges from the Supreme Court of Cassation confirmed the termination of cases terminated by the judges from the Sofia City Court, although they argued in cases when they were judges in the Sofia City Court in cases of the Ministry of Justice. They confirmed the termination of cases for millions of leva, terminated by the judges of the Kyustendil District Court, who on the other hand did not recuperate in the cases of MD. The same is confirmed by the termination of cases brought by Momchil Dobrev in the Supreme Court of Cassation, Vratsa District Court, Montana District Court, Vidin District Court, Pernik District Court.

Examples of judges from the Supreme Court of Cassation who recused themselves when they were judges in the Sofia City Court in cases with plaintiff MD or companies represented by him, such as:

ERIC VASILEV - confirms termination of a case for unjust enrichment for the amount of EUR 250,000, where thanks to judges from BRS BOS and SCC judges donate property to the D. family in the center of BURGAS for zero pennies to a non-member cooperator and expelled member. a cooperator who has been disconnected and who, two years after the termination of the JSC, has issued a notarial deed on the basis of fraud. THE PROPERTY IS GIVEN BY THE JUDGES OF THE BURGAS DISTRICT COURT, THE BURGAS DISTRICT COURT, AND THE SUPREME COURT OF CASSATION to a person from a drug mafia group for zero stotinki.

Example judges from the Supreme Court of Cassation Dragomir Dragnev, Tsonev, and dozens of others.

4.3./ EXECUTED MAFIA ORDERS FROM CRIMINAL JUDGES IN VIOLATION OF LAWS AND EVIDENCE AGAINST PEOPLE FIGHTING AGAINST THE MAFIA IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM

THE ORDERS FROM THE MAFIA ENFORCEMENT BY CRIMINAL JUDGES Goranova, Stoitsev, Vessela Evstatieva

1 /. When the judge deliberately does not allow evidence of the defense that is relevant to the accusation and assists one of the parties.

Example: Judges Stoitsev and Vanya Goranova of the Sofia District Court did not allow a reference from Raiffeisenbank - whether there was a withdrawal on 24 May 2001 and 24 May 2003 and how much, according to the pimps. AND IT IS NOTORY KNOWN THAT ON THESE DATES THE BANK BRANCHES DO NOT WORK - IT IS A HOLIDAY IN BULGARIA. The natural person against whom the ORDER OF THE MAFIA is CONVICTED BY THE TWO JUDGES STOITSEV AND VANIA GORANOVA at first instance, after which he was acquitted at second and third instance. IT TURNED OUT TO LIE TO WITNESSES

2 /. When the judge deliberately does not accept, he does not respect indisputable written evidence proving his innocence.

Example: Judge TSENOV who in the distant 2004. received the order to put a HEALTHY PERSON in the insane asylum, for which he was promised a lift in the Sofia City Court by the chairmen and deputy chairmen of the Sofia City Court Svetlin Velkov Mihailov and GEORGI KOLEV as well as a lift in the Supreme Court of Cassation by Rumen NENKOV.

Despite prepared triple, five - four expert examinations psychological - psychiatric examinations, WHICH PROVE THAT THE INDIVIDUAL IS COMPLETELY HEALTHY, Judge TSENOV does not respect them, does not accept them, and appoints another such expertise - ON ORDER.

In the end, after a year and seven months of REPRESSION by Judge TSENOV, the judges of the Sofia City Court TERMINATED THIS CASE - A SHAME ON THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM BY APOLOGIZING TO THE INDIVIDUAL FOR THIS.

3 /. Order 3

The order comes from the Chamber of Private Bailiffs chaired by Private Bailiff Georgi Saykov DICHEV.

The case of Nikolai Neykov. Prosecutor Kostadinova.

Based on a letter from the Chamber of Private Enforcement Agents signed by the Administrative Secretary Anelia Glavanova dated 01.04.2011. SGP and the city prosecutor Nikolay Kokinov and the chief prosecutor Assoc. Prof. Boris Velchev were signaled that we MD and PEA MG had committed crimes concerning Borislav Neykov and Nikolay Neykov.

The facts - the truth:

ON 25.05.2010 the company "B". - Ltd. concludes an ASSIGNMENT AGREEMENT under which the company "BOBO 5 and Sons" Ltd. transfer 10 / ten / percent of its receivables from the debtor company "Bulgarh" - Ltd. Burgas under executive sheet from 19.12.2009 on chgrd. 370/2009 of RS Knezha, for which the company pays 2000 / two thousand / BGN.

Both the assignment agreement and the receipt for the money received were signed by Nikolay Neykov personally.

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Although Nikolay Neykov and the company BOBO 5 and Sons OOD received these BGN 2,000, they filed a complaint instigated by the Private Enforcement Agents - Georgi Dichev and other PEAs in the prosecutor's office that they had been deceived by the company has not signed the assignment agreement and the receipt to it.

2 /. In addition, the person Nikolay Neykov and the company "BOBO 5 and Sons" Ltd. in a broadcast on 25.05.2011. on the state television CHANNEL 1 in the program "Open" broadcast at 22.00 spread information that they were deceived by the company and the PEA MG.

3 /. On 25.05.2011 in Valya Ahchieva's program "Openly" on Bulgarian National Television, the latter in an interview with Nikolay Neykov spread false slanderous false information about MD and MG, and this false information was confirmed and given by the National Police by police officers Ivo Savov and Vladimirova in confirmation.

A criminal case is instituted against MD.

A graphological expertise was appointed in the criminal case, which proves in an indisputable way that both the receipt and the contract were signed personally by Nikolay Neykov. In addition, Nikolay Neykov confirmed before the judge in the case that he had personally signed the contract and the receipt, ie. he himself admits that he lied throughout the pre-trial proceedings.

MD is justified ..

As a result, lawsuits have been filed against BNT, Valya Ahchieva and Neykovi - individuals and companies in cases that have disappeared since 2011. in the Sofia City Court for the dissemination of false information, false information to over 2.5 million viewers of BNT, without having the right to answer and provide evidence that everything is a FALSE LIE and INITIATED by the Chamber of Bailiffs chaired by PEA Georgi DICHEV.

4 /. Order 4

Order Against PEA MG

PEA MG introduces into its own private property the real owner, who has been using the property by a retired cop for more than 15 years without legal grounds. However, the people around the retired cop have connections with the BSP and prosecutors and the PEAs - DICHEV and others, quoted above, support this order, because the PEA MG. has complied with the law and is "accidentally" detained for 24 hours. The next day, the judge of the Sofia City Court GOT UP AND APOLOGIZED on behalf of the judiciary and ordered MG to be released immediately - a result - ruined health and many other things, irreversible, for which other people pay with something similar in other cases. Here the initiator is prosecutor Mariana Stankova, in whose office the Private Enforcement Agent - Georgi Dichev enters directly without any problems 2-3 times a week.

MG filed a lawsuit for these illegal actions of the Prosecutor's Office and the Ministry of Interior and Judge Ekaterina Encheva from the Sofia City Court terminated the case, the other case disappeared - since 2012.

5. /. THE ORDER 5 FULFILLED BY THE CRIMINAL JUDGE VESELA EVSTATIEVA FROM PLOVDIV DISTRICT COURT THE BEGINNING

On 04.04.2008 21.05.2008 by virtue of decrees for assignment D. acquire two properties located in the northern tangent of the city of Sofia - the capital of Bulgaria, respectively with areas of 2050 decares and 2170 decares.

As early as September 2008, pressure began on the father by phone from 11 pm to 3 pm, when DD was invited to donate the property of the then Prime Minister BB and threats. After these threats, DD suffered a stroke, heart attack and broke his leg in the hospital in the city of Burgas. Since September 2008, after an operation in a hospital in Sofia, DD has been in bed in Sofia.

After failing to threaten and racketeer the D. family, former State Security colonels posing as representatives of Prime Minister Boyko Borissov began to want to buy the property at a price 9,000 (nine thousand) times below the market price.

After the rejection of this proposal, actions in various institutions follow.

Following letters from the President of the Chamber of Private Enforcement Agents Private Enforcement Agent Georgi Saykov Dichev, to the National Revenue Agency, to the Prosecutor's Office, to the prosecutors Nikolay Kokinov, to Prosecutor Balev, to the Prosecutor Mariana Stankova, to the Sofia City Prosecutor's Office Mariana Stankova from the Sofia City Prosecutor's Office for appointing tax audits against the whole family and its companies.

After colonels from State Security 2010 and 2011 with an office on Vitosha Blvd. - in the city of Sofia, they offered a former boarding house to the D. family and introduced themselves on behalf of BOYKO BORISOV and offered to buy these lands owned by the D family at a price of 9000 / nine thousands / times below market value?!?!,

And after the members of the D. family refused to sell these lands to the NRA and the prosecutor's office was activated, tax audits began, orders of prosecutor Mariana Stankova for tax audits, foreclosures on all properties of the D. family followed, as well as the process lands 2050 decares and 2170 decares.

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The National Revenue Agency is asking the son of the MD family for unpaid taxes for BGN 2,000,000 / two million / BGN 6,000,000 / six million / BGN 8,000,000 / eight million,

Taxes in the amount of BGN 2,000,000 are demanded from father D and BGN 2,000,000 / two million / from the mother.

THE AUDITS OF THE NATIONAL REVENUE AGENCY IN BULGARIA ENDED WITH AUDIT ACTS FROM WHICH IT IS SHOWN THAT THE PERSONS OF THE FAMILY D. DO NOT OWE ANY CENT OF THE STATE.

Following a complaint from a person representing the support of the GERB party and the MRF party Krassimir Mollov, a prosecutor's file was opened. There are also letters from the President of the Chamber of Private Enforcement Agents Georgi Saykov Dichev to the Prosecutor's Office, the National Revenue Agency, and the Sofia City Prosecutor's Office.

In 2011 the apartment of the D family was set on fire, in 2012 at the beginning of the year a bus was waiting for MD next to his office to push and smash it, but it only passed through his leg. After seven more assassination attempts on MD.

Following is an attempt to steal private property through a Concession by the Council of Ministers with Prime Ministers SERGEY STANISHEV 2009 and Prime Minister BOYKO BORISOV 2010. By Decision of the COUNCIL OF MINISTERS № 43 of 23.01.2009. with Prime Minister Sergey Stanishev and subsequently with Decision № 69 of 15.02.2010 with Prime Minister Boyko Borisov decides to enter into an ILLEGAL CONCESSION with the company "CELSIAN" on properties PRIVATE PROPERTY for 35 years, as the Council of Ministers has determined and given LAND - additional to the concession area of 2 928.5 in the amount of additional area of 9 084 decares PRIVATE PROPERTY.

THE PURPOSE IS THE THEFT OF THE PRIVATE LANDS, which back in 2008 the then mayor of Sofia Boyko Borisov announced as his own lands on which he would build a super settlement. 2010 and 2011 the requests for a Detailed Development Plan in the UAGC of Sofia Municipality for the preparation of a detailed development plan DO NOT ACCIDENTALLY DISAPPEAR and so far they do not exist. There are projects to build a power plant for 375 megawatts based on the technologies created in 1991 by MD, stadiums, complexes and others for 5 billion dollars.

4.2./ EVIDENCE FOR EXECUTION OF ORDERS FROM JUDGES in one court process and one court case. / IN CIVIL AND COMMERCIAL CASES

EVIDENCE OF MAFIOTIZATION OF THE COURT, CRIMINAL LAWLESSNESS OF JUDGES, DOUBLE STANDARD OF JUDGES, REPRESSION, COORDINATION.

EXAMPLES:

Judges Lyubka Golakova, Alexander Emilov ANGELOV, and Svetlana Atanasova of the Sofia City Court deliberately ruled in retroactive effect of an already entered court decision with the same subject matter. 7033/2012 dated 12.11.2018. - contrary to the entered into force court decision on civil case 53552/2016 dated 16.11.2016. of Judge Daniela Stoeva, although they were notified of the entry into force of a court decision.

LOSSES for \$ 11 million.

Judge Raina Martinova of the Sofia City Court did NOT EVEN mention ANY ATTACHED WRITTEN EVIDENCE, did not even discuss it in her decision, and impartial - they are NOT EVEN MENTIONED, in civil case 1919/2016 according to the inventory of the Sofia City Court, Decision of 03.01.2019. and a case in which a reduction of the claim of BGN 9,900 was made and Judge Raina Martinova deliberately did not send the case to the jurisdiction of the Sofia District Court - apparently in execution of the order.

Judge Vladimir Valkov of the Sofia City Court supports and assists the respondent - Insurance Company, helping it what actions to take, what to object, what to appeal and challenge, which are excluded from the law - Judge Vladimir Valkov in case against 10868/2010 against Insurer, the same was confirmed and done in another case by Judge Tahchieva of the Sofia Court of Appeal.

Judge EVGENI GEORGIEV of the Sofia City Court knowingly exempts a party from paying a state fee when the country belongs to the mafia - in this case the Kremikovtzi case, in a case in which a state fee of over 3.2 million euros is due, the same is done by Judge Albena Boteva from Sofia City Court confirmed these actions - in a civil case.

Judge Raina Martinova of the Sofia City Court knowingly REPLACED SECURITY - DEFICIENCY OF THE DEFENDANT'S PROPERTY - CONSTRUCTION COMPANY on a claim for a principal of EUR 175,000 against a guarantee paid by the defendant only for the amount of EUR 2,500. pay judges, to lose cases against them - case - Order of 23.03.2018 on civil case 10535/2017 Sofia City Court 1 - 18 panel of Judge Raina Martinova, this decision was confirmed by the Sofia Court of Appeal on chgr. 2960/2018 dated 23.07.2018 of judges Nelly Kutzkova, Diana Koledzhikova and Dimitar Mirchev, as well as Nelly Kutzkova and Dimitar Mirchev recused themselves in a case of the same construction company, as a man of the company petitioned the judge's husband Nelly

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Kutzkova, especially that judges Nelly Kutzkova and Dimitar Mirchev objected to other cases of MD. - GUARANTEED LOSS OF OVER 550,000 EUR.

Upon application under Art. 410 of the Civil Procedure Code for issuing a writ of execution against the company KREMIKOVTSI - AD, in which the father of the President of the Sofia City Court Svetlin Velkov Mihailov has shares, for amounts of EUR 17,615 and amounts of EUR 1,187,542 heard by Judge Svetlin Velkov Mihailov - then chairman of Sofia City Court the cases disappear and the respective writs of execution are not issued for the respective amounts. LOSSES OVER 2,500,000 EUROS.

Objections to unaccepted receivables under item 95/2007 of the Sofia City Court disappear - fees for millions of leva and a liability in the amount of EUR 2,100,000 to a company on the part of the debtor Kremikovtzi - losses of over EUR 8 million without interest.

Judge Ivo Vatev VATEV - TENS OF CASES

He deliberately ends lawsuits against companies of people in the mafia who are proud of the fact that for more than 10 / ten / years that he pays judges, prosecutors, tax and when there are cases, inspections and others against them, with perfect evidence of this is a judge. Judge Ivo Vatev Vatev, case No. 70844/2018 of the SCC - 127 panel of the SCC, confirmed by order No 9943 dated 29.06.2020 under Chgrd. 8594/2019 of judges Vladimir Valkov, Eelitsa Yordanova, Alexander Angelov - Sofia City Court, provided that judges Vladimir Valkov and Alexander Angelov recused themselves in other cases of the Ministry of Justice.

4.3.2. THE FIRST EVIDENCE FOR FULFILLMENT OF THE ORDER OF THE MAFIA AGAINST MG AND MD - THE ORDER OF THE JUDGES FROM THE SUPREME COURT OF CASSATION - RUZHENA KERANOVA, NIKOLAI DARMONSKI AND VALYA RUSHA.

JUDGES of the Supreme Court of Cassation RUZHENA KERANOVA, NIKOLAI DARMONSKI and VALYA RUSHANOVA on April 28, 2017. send the case to look into the nearest SOFIA CITY COURT - Plovdiv Regional Court - although the District Court of Sofia, Pernik District Court District Court Blagoevgrad District court Kyustendil, even DISTRICT COURT PAZARDZHIC are closer to Sofia than DISTRICT COURT PLOVDIV, because there the influence of the then Chief Prosecutor SOTIR TSATSAROV is understandable. The distance to the Plovdiv District Court is 138 km, and to the district courts - Sofia District Court - 0 meters, Pernik - 15 km, Pazardzhik - 100 km, Blagoevgrad 90 km, Kyustendil 70 km.

4.3.2.1. EXECUTION THE MAFIA'S ORDER proved by the ACTIONS of the criminal judge VESELA EVSTATIEVA from the Plovdiv District Court with the ultimate goal of stealing private property for 8 billion euros.

This order was initiated by letters from the Chamber of Private Enforcement Agents, PEA Dichev as its chairman, other 4 - PEAs qualified as financiers and prepared a Financial Report - fraud.

Prosecutor Mariana Stankova, a well-known prosecutor, instituted pre-trial proceedings against Chaset Bailiff MG for having entered a decision to award a buyer, which was entered by the buyer himself and not by the PEA.

The indictment also contains the accusation that PEA MG sold foreign properties without taking a foreclosure from PEA MG. from 30.08.2007 and the properties were sold to the public, and the debtor KREMIKOVC AD sold the FORBIDDEN PROPERTIES by PEA MG on 30.08.2007 September and November 2007 to third parties.

Instead of ACCUSING THE MANAGERS OF KREMIKOVTSI AD of SELLING FORBIDDEN PROPERTIES by PEAs to third parties, the exact opposite is being done.

THE ORDER IS PROVEN: Filing a charge, which is accompanied by THREATS OF RACKETS, EXTORTION FROM PEOPLE CLOSE TO THE GOVERNMENT AND THE MAFIA, who threaten and DEMAND MONEY and property.

After the judges of the Sofia City Court recused themselves, the execution of the order by the judges of the Supreme Court of Cassation followed, namely:

JUDGES of the Supreme Court of Cassation RUZHENA KERANOVA, NIKOLAI DARMONSKI and VALYA RUSHANOVA on April 28, 2017. send the case to BE SEED IN THE "NEAREST" TO SOFIA CITY COURT COURT - IN PLOVDIV DISTRICT COURT 145 km - despite the fact that Sofia District Court - 0 km, DISTRICT COURT PERNIK IN BULGARIA - 23 km KYUSTENDIL - 70 km, Even PAZARDZHIC DISTRICT COURT - 100 km are closer to SOFIA than PLOVDIV DISTRICT COURT, because there the influence of the then Chief Prosecutor SOTIR TSATSAROV is understandable.

In Plovdiv, the first judge found a lady to withdraw from the case, OBVIOUSLY he took measures so as not to be forced to DO ILLEGAL THINGS.

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On July 9, 2020, on behalf of KRASIMIR MOLLOV, under the protection of the GERB parties of Boyko Borissov and MRF of Ahmed Dogan, that the execution of the order by the judge hearing on the criminal case in Plovdiv on July 23, 2002 agitation by journalists, WHICH HAPPENED - the journalist VALYA AHCHIEVA, THAT HE PAYED THE JUDGE TO SENTENCE MD and MG that THE JUDGE WILL ACCEPT ALL FALSESIES will again be fraud, that the judge would refuse the appointment of honest eXPERTISE THAT WILL JUDGE appoint requested report and the evidence that the judge will like interviewing witnesses with false statements, the judge will appoint experts who draw FALSE expertise

That the judge will not obey the law, will break it, will not respect the law,

THE PERFORMED ORDER is also confirmed by the legal adviser of Kremikovtzi CHOBANOV in the show of the journalist VALYA AHCHIEVA, broadcast on various media on September 15, 2020 and SEE BY MILLIONS OF VIEWERS ON THE INTERNET AND ON THE WATCH, it will last - I hope it will last.

It is no coincidence that the first judge Milev was taken away because we were told that there was pressure on him to convict us, although he said in the courtroom that there was NO LEGAL FRAMEWORK and subject matter in the case to look at him.

It is no coincidence that the criminal case is on the complaint of Krassimir A Senov Mollov, who since September 2008. and so far he is FORCING MD to TRANSFER 30% of his land WITHOUT MONEY.

Judge VESELA EVSTATIEVA, who twice returned the indictment to the Sofia City Prosecutor's Office in the person of Prosecutor NINA YANEVA, for the third time refused to return the indictment, ALTHOUGH IT WAS 100% IDENTICAL TO THE PREVIOUS ONE WHO WAS RETURNING.

This is the beginning of the execution of the order by Judge Vessela EVSTATIEVA.

The criminal case is TAKEN BY THE WORDS OF THE PEOPLE OF THE MAFIA and Kremikovtzi by Judge VESELA EVSTATIEVA of the Plovdiv District Court, who HAS TAKEN THE CASE - we quote the words of the persons, and the same judge WAS NOT ELECTED BY CASE.

JUDGE EVSTATIEVA, who, in the words of the people of the MAFIA, "ACCEPTED TO WATCH THE CASE", FULFILLS THE ORDER OF THE MAFIA to convict in the indisputable evidence of the opposite - innocence.

EVIDENCE FOR THE ORDER OF THE MAFIA FROM THE CRIMINAL JUDGE VESELA EVSTATIEVA from Plovdiv District Court Here we quote some of the things proving the execution of the order.

1/. Judge EVSTATIEVA deliberately erred in treating indisputable evidence - Judge Evstatieva of the PSC when there was an injunction on 30.08.2007. of property to a debtor from the PEA and despite this foreclosure Kremikovtzi sold in September 2007 and November 2007. PROHIBITED properties of third parties. THE JUDGE OF THE ORDER OF THE MAFIA VESELA EVSTATIEVA DID NOT MENTION THIS PROHIBITION AT ALL FROM 30.08.2007.

2/. Judge Evstatieva's testimony confirming the correct actions of the PEA confirms the testimony of a witness that these were violations - despite the court decision of the SCC, which proves the RIGHTS of the PEA and the fees due to her.

3/. JUDGE VESELA EVSTATIEVA DID NOT READ UNCONDITIONAL EVIDENCE FROM THE NATIONAL REVENUE AGENCY AND THE NATIONAL INSURANCE INSTITUTE OF BULGARIA THAT THE PERSON MD 2010 HE IS NOT AN EMPLOYEE OF PEA MG €

4/. JUDGE VESELA EVSTATIEVA DID NOT READ THE EXPERTISE WHO QUOTES BANK TRANSFERS AND PAID MONEY ON THE PUBLIC SOLD, DOES NOT READ DOCUMENTS FOR AMOUNTS AMOUNTED ON THE CASH REGISTER

It's the same as.

Example: Judge TSENOV who in the distant 2004. received the order to put a completely HEALTHY PERSON in the insane asylum, for which he was promised a lift in the Sofia City Court by Svetlio and Joro, as well as a lift in the Supreme Court of Cassation by Rumen.

Despite the preparation of triple, five - four expert examinations psychological - psychiatric examinations, Judge TSENOV does not respect them, does not accept them, and appoints another such expertise - ORDERS FROM A JUDGE.

5/. Judge EVSTATIEVA deliberately fails to enforce a court decision that has entered into force, deliberately issues a decision in retroactive effect of a court decision that has already entered into force with the same subject matter and the same case.

6/. the judge deliberately does not apply the law because the defendant is his fellow judge on the example of

Example Judge Kacherilska from the SRS terminates

7/. Judge EVSTATIEVA deliberately disregards decrees of other institutions such as the National Revenue Agency - ENTRY INTO FORCE, REVISION ACTS - ENTRY INTO FORCE FOR AMOUNTS PAID ON PUBLIC SOLD.

8/. JUDGE EVSTATIEVA did not even comment on the indisputable oral evidence gathered

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9/. Judge EVSTATIEVA disregards a court decision which has already entered into force and is binding on him in connection with the subject matter of the present case.

10/. JUDGE EVSTATIEVA DOES NOT EVEN MENTION ANY ATTACHED WRITTEN EVIDENCE, DOES NOT EVEN DISCUSS THEM IN HIS DECISION, THERE ARE NO REASONS, NO EVIDENCE HAS BEEN DISCUSSED -

11/. JUDGE EVSTATIEVA does not admit evidence, does not quote, DOES NOT EVEN MENTION THE TESTIMONY of the witnesses which are objective and impartial - THEY DO NOT EVEN MENTION

12/. JUDGE EVSTATIEVA knowingly DOES NOT ALLOW EVIDENCE CONCERNING THE SUBJECT OF THE CASE

13 /. JUDGE EVSTATIEVA CONSCIOUSLY DOES NOT ATTACH THE RELEVANT ACTION TO THE RELEVANT ARTICLE OF THE CRIMINAL CODE AND INVENTS HIMSELF AND GOES TO THE MOST STRICT CORRESPONDENCE.

14 /. JUDGE EVSTATIEVA, in case of indisputable evidence of forgery of documents, clearly and provenly in the Prosecutor's Office of the Sofia City Prosecutor's Office by the PROSECUTORS, did NOT APPOINT AN EXPERTISE and continued to use these forged documents

15 /. JUDGE VESELA EVSTATIEVA, although one EVIDENCE two enforcement cases are COMPROMISED - SEIZED IN VIOLATION OF THE LAW AND BY LAW THEY CANNOT BE USED, EVEN MORE THAN THEY ARE EXECUTIVE IN this VESELA EVSTATIEVA DOES NOT EXCLUDE THESE COMPROMISED FALSE EVIDENCE FROM THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE, but USES THEM - AGAIN IN VIOLATION OF THE LAW.

16 /. In the case presided over by JUDGE VESELA EVSTATIEVA, enclosed written evidence over 69 pages that exonerate the defendants disappeared, and despite the missing documents in the subsequent application of the documents, Judge Evstatieva did not accept them and did not appoint an investigation into who stole the documents.

17 /. Despite the entry into force, it was decided by the Sofia City Court, which proves the lawful actions of the Private Enforcement Agents M.G. Judge Evstatieva treated the decision retroactively in the testimony of a witness.

18 /. Judge VESELA EVSTATIEVA knowingly wrongly treated indisputable evidence when there was an injunction on 30.08.2007. of property to a debtor from the PEA and despite this foreclosure Kremikovtzi sold in September 2007 and November 2007. foreclosed properties of third parties.

19 / .Judge EVSTATIEVA and knowingly with indisputable evidence that forgery of documents was committed openly and proven in the prosecutor's office Sofia City Prosecutor's Office, does not appoint an expert and continues to use these forged documents.

20/. Judge EVSTATIEVA knowingly erred in treating written evidence - an effective court decision.

21/. Judge EVSTATIEVA deliberately uncontroverted evidence that they have committed falsification of documents were obvious and PROVEN WHEN THEY WERE IN PROSECUTION - the Sofia City Prosecutor's Office by one of the supervising prosecutors - Stankova Damitrova or Yaneva or anyone else not to appoint expertise and continues to use these counterfeit documents.

22/. In the case of Judge EVSTATIEVA, enclosed written evidence of more than 69 pages disappearing, which exonerates the defendants, and despite the missing documents in the subsequent application of the documents, Judge Evstatieva did not accept them deliberately and did not appoint an investigation into who stole the documents.

23/. Despite the entry into force, it was decided by the Sofia City Court, which proves the lawful actions of the Private Enforcement Agents M.G. Judge Evstatieva treated the decision retroactively in the testimony of a witness.

24/. Judge EVSTATIEVA does not respect the law and does not obey its spirit, deliberately changes the content and adds to the law, deliberately misapplies the law, deliberately does not quote the law, deliberately misinterprets the law, deliberately misinterprets laws - example old CPC with new CPC, deliberately wrong replaces laws - an example of an old CPC with a new CPC

25/. Judge EVSTATIEVA deliberately erred in treating indisputable evidence - Judge Evstatieva of the POS when there was an injunction on 30.08.2007. of property to a debtor from the Private Enforcement Agents and despite this foreclosure Kremikovtzi sold in September 2007 and November 2007. PREVIOUSLY FORBIDDEN PROPERTIES OF THIRD PARTIES - WHICH IS A CRIME UNDER THE CRIMINAL CODE.

Instead of bringing charges against the management of KREMIKOVTSI who have sold property confiscated from PMI, the prosecutor's office in the person of prosecutor MARIYANA STANKOVA, DANIELA DIMITROVA, NINA YANEVA has accused Proga from Sofia.

26/. When on the basis of a decision of the Sofia City Court confirming the correct actions of the PEA, Judge Evstatieva confirmed the testimony of a witness that these were violations - despite the court decision of the Sofia City Court.

27/. Judge VESELA EVSTATIEVA knowingly did not allow evidence of the defense that is relevant to the accusation and assisted one of the parties.

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Example: Judges Stoitsev and Vanya Goranova of the SRS do not allow information from Raiffeisenbank - whether there was a withdrawal of money and cork on 24 May 2001 and 24 May 2003, according to the pimps. AND IT IS NOTORY KNOWN THAT ON THESE DATES THE BANK BRANCHES DO NOT WORK - HOLIDAY E. Momchil Dobrev was SENTENCED by both judges, after which he was acquitted at the second and third instance.

Judges Stoitsev and Vanya Goranova deliberately did not allow the requested reference.

28/. Judge EVSTATIEVA knowingly does not accept, does not respect indisputable written evidence proving innocence

29/. JUDGE VESELA EVSTATIVA DOES NOT READ BANK PAYMENT DOCUMENTS PROVING THAT THE PROPERTIES HAVE BEEN PAID.

4.4. Parallel action of the mafia in court - Sofia City Court Presidents KALOYAN Topalov POPKOLEVA and ALEKSEY TRIFONOV and Sofia Regional Court - Judge CLAUDIA MITOVA, judge CHEHLAROV supported by the MAFIA and Supreme COURT WAITING CRIMINAL case in which JUDGE EVSTATIEVA MUST MADE AN ORDER AGAINST THE ACCUSED TO PLEASE THEM WITH THE END OF THE PURPOSE OF BILLION PROPERTIES FOR BILLIONS.

FOR EIGHT YEARS, THERE HAS NOT BEEN A SINGLE COURT SESSION IN THE CASES SUBMITTED BY THE MAFIA ILLEGALLY, IN VIOLATED BY LAW by Kremikovtzi in civil case 1685/2013, 6694/2013, 1943/2013 with judges Vladimir Malenarov, ALA Vallelov, Boteva, and instead of the cases being terminated by law, the mafia is exempted from paying millions of euros in state fees, the properties are banned and the real owners managed by American companies CANNOT DISPOSE of the properties -

LOST INVESTMENT FOR € 5 BILLION €

KREMIKOVTSI AD takes over 2013. commercial cases for all purchased and PAID PROPERTIES.

However, instead of the cases being terminated by the JUDGES OF THE SOFIA CITY COURT, who PROVENLY FULFILLED THE ORDER OF THE MAFIA, the cases are not commercial, and the same cases were filed in violation of the law only 5 / five / years after the issuance of the procedural act and four years after of the plaintiff KREMIKOVTSI in bankruptcy.

In reality, under the commercial law, Kremikovtzi will not have the right to conduct these cases, and if it has filed them, THE CASES ARE OVERDUE - four years AFTER THE APPLICABLE - THE MANDATORY TERM of one year after declaring Kremikovtzi bankrupt, ie. May 2009 .

FOR MORE THAN 8 / EIGHT / years the judges VLADIMIR VALKOV, RAYNA MARTINOVA, ALBENA BOTEVA, LYUBKA GOLAKOVA, ALEXANDER ANGELOV from the Sofia City Court have not terminated the cases.

And this despite the fact that the judges VLADIMIR VALKOV, RAINA MARTINOVA, ALBENA BOTEVA, ALEXANDER ANGELOV recused themselves in other cases for one of the parties.

The refusal to terminate cases and to fulfill the law is confirmed by the judges of the second instance Sofia Appellate Court - judges Koutskova Ivanka Angelova, KRASIMIR MASHEV golden RUBIEVA Daniela DONCHEVA Nelly Koutskova, YANA Valdobrev, Nikolai MITANOV, MADLEN JELEVA, Galina Ivanova, Vasil Hristakieva , ATANAS KEMANOV, ASEN VODENICHAROV IVAN IVANOV.

Moreover judges Koutskova, Ivanka Angelova, KRASIMIR MASHEV golden RUBIEVA Daniela DONCHEVA Nelly Koutskova, YANA Valdobrev, Nikolai MITANOV, Galina Ivanova, Vasil Hristakieva, ATANAS KEMANOV, ASSEN VODENICHAROV have given arresters in cases of family D when they are were judges in lower courts - SOFISKI GRADSKI SA. Instead of withdrawing from these cases, THEY CONFIRM THE REFUSALS TO TERMINATE THE CASE

THIS IS A VIOLATION OF EUROPEAN LAW and unscrupulous proof of a contract.

ALL PROPERTIES for which investments in the amount of 5 billion US dollars have been prepared by AMERICAN COMPANIES, the claims have been entered and the real owners can do nothing - NO INVESTMENTS, NO INVESTMENT INVESTMENT.

Moreover, the judges from Sofia Gradski Court Evgeni GEORGIEV exempts KREMIKOVTSI from paying millions of euros due state fees, WHICH IS ANOTHER CRIME COMMITTED BY A JUDGE, which was confirmed by Judge NELI K.

THE BUDGET OF THE REPUBLIC OF BULGARIA WAS DAMAGED BY MILLIONS OF EUROS.

And this happened in the Sofia City Court, when the presidents of the judges ALEKSEY TRIFONOV, KALOYAN TOPALOV, POPKOLEVA, IF EVGENI GEORGIEV, YANEVA, Presidents of the Sofia Court of Appeal, DANEGOV DANCHI.

Judge Claudia MITOVA from the Sofia District Court did not even close the case for two properties that KREMIKOVTSI had actually sold, and no real owners, and DESPITE THIS, THEY ARE LEARNING THIS CASE, JUST TO DAMAGE € FOR DAMAGE -

Judge KLAUDIA MITOVA herself, a former prosecutor from the SRS in the case, stated that ALL JUDGES FOLLOW the criminal case in PLOVDIV, and are guided by gova.

THAT IS WHY THERE HAS BEEN NO COURT SESSION FOR MORE THAN 8 / EIGHT / YEARS in the cases filed by KREMIKOVTSI.

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le THE EXECUTION OF THE ORDER FROM JUDGE VESELA EVSTATIEVA FROM PLOVDIV IS WAITING FOR THE EXECUTION OF THESE CIVIL CASES.

4.5 /. THE INACTION OF THE CHIEF PROSECUTOR IVAN GESHEV, the Chairperson of the Plovdiv District Court Sheitanova and Deputy The chairwoman MARIA SHISHKOVA - close to SOTIR TSATSAROV

The inaction of the members of the Supreme Judicial Council and Inspector TOCHKOVA.

Despite dozens of signals with attached evidence of OBVIOUS VIOLATIONS and EXPRESS AND PROVEN CRIMES committed by Prosecutor NINA YANEVA, Prosecutor MARIANA STANKOVA, Judge VESELA EVSTATIEVA or Chief Prosecutor IVAN and Deputy Presidents IVAN GESHE. The President of the Plovdiv District Court SHEYTANOVA and Judge MARIA SHISHKOVA close to the former Chief Prosecutor SOTIR TSATSAROV and his former deputy. Chief Prosecutor, DO NOT IMPLEMENT Art. 312 of the Judiciary Act and do not want reprimand for Judge VESELA EVSTATIEVA - her disciplinary dismissal.

5/. TERMINATION AND DISAPPEARANCE OF CASES AGAINST BANKS FOR HUNDREDS OF MILLIONS OF EUROS, INSURERS FOR TENS OF MILLIONS OF EUROS, FOR STOLEN PROPERTIES AND FACTORIES FOR EUROS

1 /. The judges of the SRS - Alexander Emilov Angelov, Vladimir Valkov, terminated cases for stolen property from EMIL KYULEV in the center of Sofia - hereditary property of heirs with a market value of over 600 million euros. Through a notary - Rumen Dimitrov - the properties were stolen by EMIL KYULEV.

2 /. A lawsuit against UNICREDIT BULBANK for \$ 230 MILLION has disappeared in Sofia City Court.

3 /. A case against SiBANK has disappeared, now UBB - for 1.5 million euros.

4 /. Missing cases against insurers DZI, BULSTRAD Vienna Insurance GROUP, and other insurers for tens of millions of euros.

5 /. Missing cases against Private Enforcement Agent Geori Saikov Dichev, PEA Ivan Todorov Tsolakov, and other PEAs for tens of millions of euros.

6 /. Missing cases for dozens of properties in downtown Sofia worth 600m euros.

7 /. A case for 250 billion euros in the Sofia City Court has disappeared

8 /. property through a notary and legalized by judges from BRS, Boss and SCC

9 /. Missing cases against the judge of the Sofia City Court YORDANKA BORISOVA MOLLOVA and her brother lawyer HRISTO BORISOV MOLLOV for misappropriated slot machines and BINGO equipment for millions of euros.

10 /. Case 17265/2012 disappears according to the inventory of the Sofia District Court concerning the ownership of a property in the center of Sofia - a four-storey building, with plans to build an 8-storey building and an investment of 9 million euros, stolen by an oligarch. as the case is heard by Judge CHEKHLAROV, who keeps the case with him and for more than 0 / nine / years the real owners do not have access to the case, they cannot see it, they do not receive the requested certificates.

11 /. Case 1066/2010 on the list of the Sofia District Court with presiding judge CHEKHLAROV, protege of the Varna group of three letters, owned by banks, insurance companies, companies in Bulgaria, for ownership of an apartment in Sofia purchased from a public sale, disappears. Judge CHEKHLAROV is hiding the case, the parties have no access to the case file.

12 /. Cases for properties stolen by EMIL KYULEV through FALSE notaries disappear

13 /. Disappears cases of private property stolen by the CITY MUNICIPALITY with Mayor first STEFAN SOFIANSKI, then with Mayor BOYKO BORISOV, then by Mayor FANDAKOVA, who issued municipal property deeds for PRIVATE PROPERTIES. WHICH IS A THEFT.

6/. SCHEMES AND EVIDENCE FOR TERMINATION OF LAWSUITS In the Sofia District Court on lawsuits by which judges have attributed crimes, have accused citizens of committing a crime that they have not committed

Judge PETYA TOPALOVA terminates a lawsuit against judges Ivanka Nikolova Angelova, Krassimir Atanasov Mashev, Zlatina Georgieva Rubieva from the Sofia Court of Appeal, Lyubka Emilova Golakova from Sofia District, Sofia District Court crimes, have accused citizens of committing crimes WHICH THEY HAVE NOT COMMITTED

According to Chnhd 1002/2019 - Penal Code of the Sofia District Court Judge MARIA SHOYLEKOVA - MARINOVA does the same

Judge ALBENA DOYNOVA of the Sofia District Court did the same in a lawsuit against Judges Penka Bratanova, Miroslav Nachev and Veselina Dzhoneva.

Judge KRASIMIRA PRODANOVA terminated a lawsuit against a judge of the Sofia City Court Albena Boteva for defamation, attributing a crime that the citizen did not commit.

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According to Chnhd 17397/2019 - Criminal Code of the Sofia District Court Judge RADOSLAVA KACHERILSKA termination of a lawsuit against a judge of the Sofia City Court ELITSA YORDANOVA

According to Chnhd 7309/2019 - Criminal Code of the SRS Judge RADOSLAVA KACHERILSKA termination of a lawsuit against Judges PENKA BRATANOVA, TATYANA KOSTADINOVA, SIMONA NAVUSHANOVA of the Kyustendil District Court

And two other chnhd terminated by Judge RADOSLAVA KACHERILSKA.

According to Nohd 4921/2020 - 17th panel according to the list of the Sofia District Court Judge Radoslava Kacherilaska does not recuperate

According to Chnhd 7307/2019 - Judge RADOSLAVA KACHERILSKA terminates the lawsuit against the judges of the Sofia City Court - ALBENA BOTEVA, RAINA MARTINOVA, ALEXANDER ANGELOV.

According to Chnhd 19079/2019 - Judge PETAR SLAVCHEV from the Sofia District Court terminated the lawsuit against the judge from the Sofia City Court - SVILEN STANCHEV IVANOV.

Judge PETROSLAV KANEV from the Sofia District Court terminated the lawsuit against Judge VLADIMIR STANCHEV KANEV under Chnhd 2149/2020 - - 99 panel.

According to chnhd 12002/2019

Judge Iliana Pashkova terminated a lawsuit against the judges of the Sofia Court of Appeals Diana Koledzhikova, Kamelia Parvanova, Dimitar Mirchev and Judge Lyubka Golakova of the Sofia City Court under the 20048/2019 Criminal Chamber of the Sofia District Court.

The termination of the lawsuits is confirmed as a violation of the law by judges of the Sofia City Court, although by law they are not allowed to file lawsuits against their colleagues from the same court.

Judges of the Sofia City Court Rusi ALEKSIEV, IVAN KOEV and Jr. The village of KONSTANTINA HRISTOVA confirmed the termination of the lawsuits filed against their colleagues by the Sofia City Court.

THE CONCLUSION - BULGARIAN JUDGES CAN WRITE ANYTHINGS, - insult you, slander you, attribute crimes to citizens who have not committed crimes committed by the city.

THERE IS NO JUSTICE - THERE IS NO JUSTICE - THERE IS NO LAW FOR THEM.

7/. THE MAFIOTIZATION OF THE COURT SCHEMES FOR TERMINATION OF CASES, PROVING ORDERS PERFORMED AND EXECUTED BY JUDGES in favor of a state, third parties and others.

CRIMINAL LAWLESSNESS, ORDERS, REPRESSIONS, RACKETS, COORDINATION?!?!?!?

Examples of schemes of judges from the Sofia City Court and the Sofia District Court who terminate cases without grounds, unscrupulously, in violation of the laws of the state.

1 / . FIRST SCHEME - TERMINATION OF CASES.

Judge LYUBKA GOLAKOVA of the Sofia City Court issued an order, which must be satisfied within 7 or 14 days. IN BUSINESS, THE CASE WILL NOT BE UNDERSTANDABLE WHAT SHOULD BE SATISFIED. Access to the case is requested, it is not given.

THE CASE IS TERMINATED.

ALL THIS IS KNOWN BY THE PRESIDENT ALEKSEY TRIFONOV of the Sofia City Court AND HE DOES NOT TAKE ANY MEASURES AND ACTIONS against the judges.

2 / . SECOND SCHEME - TERMINATION OF CASES Judge LYUBKA GOLAKOVA.

A judge from the Sofia City Court WRITES that the statement of claim and the evidence have not been signed, WHICH IS NOT TRUE. AS WELL AS THE CLAIM IS THE EVIDENCE.

AT THE SAME TIME, THE CASE IS NOT IN THE RECORD. NO ACCESS TO HIM.

3 / . THIRD SCHEME - HOW TO EXCLUDE EVIDENCE FROM A CASE !!!

Judge LYUBKA GOLAKOVA sends an order that the written evidence has not been signed and MUST BE CERTIFIED !!! THE CASE IS MISSING IN THE RECORDS.

4 / . FOURTH SCHEME for termination of cases by judges IVOV VATEV VATEV, HRISTO KRACHUNOV

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4.1./In Civil Case 79573 / 2017- 127 panel of the Sofia District Court - Judge Ivo Vatev Vatev issued an Order dated 10.10.2018, by which JUDGE IVOV VATEV VATEV returned my claim.

Judge Vatev cites that he SENT INSTRUCTIONS dated October 9, 2018. , WHICH HAS REALLY NEVER BEEN ISSUED AND HAS NOT DELIVERED. ie THIS IS A FRAUD. IT ALREADY HAS HIS INSTRUCTIONS from 09.10.2018. -- WHAT IN THE CASE THERE ARE NO ONES and on the date 10.10.2018. the same returns the claim.

4.2 / .In Civil Case 85919 / 2017- 127 panel of Judge IVO VATEV VATEV
It issues an Order dated 10.10.2018, which returns my claim, there is no order

4.3./In Civil Case 23302 / 2017- 127 panel of Judge Ivo Vatev Vatev ruled Order № 550824 of 02.12.2018 no order

4.4./ On Civil Case 47494 / 2018- 127 panel of the Sofia District Court Judge Ivo Vatev Vatev issued Order № 544710 of 25.11.2018

The same quotes that HE SENT INSTRUCTIONS from 04.06.2018, WHICH HAS REALLY NEVER ISSUED AND HAVE NOT DELIVERED. ie there are no such instructions in the case.

4.5./ In Civil Case 63137 / 2018- 127 panel of the Sofia District Court Judge Ivo Vatev Vatev issued Order № 537673 of 17.11.2018 returning my claim

The same quotes that HE SENT INSTRUCTIONS from 04.06.2018, WHICH HAS REALLY NEVER ISSUED AND HAVE NOT DELIVERED. ie there are no such instructions in the case.

4.6./ In civil case 70844 / 2018- 127 panel of the SCC Judge Ivo Vatev Vatev issued Order № 562797 of 16.12.2018

The same quotes that HE SENT INSTRUCTIONS from 02.07.2018, WHICH HAS REALLY NEVER ISSUED AND HAVE NOT DELIVERED. ie there are no such instructions in the case.

4.7./In civil case 79573 / 2017- 127 panel Judge Ivo Vatev Vatev issued an Order dated 10.10.2018, which returned my claim. The same quotes that HE SENT INSTRUCTIONS from 09.10.2018. , WHICH HAS REALLY NEVER BEEN ISSUED AND HAS NOT DELIVERED. THIS IS A SCAM

4.8./ In Civil Case 82232 / 2017- 127 panel of the SCC Judge Ivo Vatev Vatev ruled Order of 10.10.2018 returned my claim against the former judge Yordanka Borisova Mollova

The same quotes that HE SENT INSTRUCTIONS from 13.10.2018. WHICH HAS REALLY NEVER BEEN ISSUED AND HAS NOT BEEN DELIVERED.

WHAT TO TALK. HE ISSUED INSTRUCTIONS from 13.10.2018. WHICH HAS ALREADY SENT AND AFTER THAT HAVE ALREADY BEEN "RECEIVED" ON THE DATE 10.10.2018. - ie before the date of the instructions and the sending WITH ORDER RETURNS THE CLAIM.

THIS IS COMPLETELY ABSURD.

4.9 / . In Civil Case 18342 / 2018- 127 panel of the SCC Judge Ivo Vatev Vatev issued Order № 67169 of 17.03.2019, which returned my claim

The same quotes that HE SENT INSTRUCTIONS from 12.02.2018, WHICH HAS REALLY NEVER ISSUED AND HAVE NOT SERVED. ie there are no such instructions in the case.

4.10./ In civil case 17070/2018 - 169 panel of the SCC Judge VESELINA IVANOVA DIMCHEVA ruled Order № 14396 of 17.01.2019 returned my claim

4.11./ THIRD IMPOSED mafia PRACTICE. From the materials in the case there is an old tax assessment from which it is evident that the tax assessment of the property is over BGN 90,000 / ninety thousand /, WHICH MEANS THAT THE CASE IS JURISDICTION TO THE SOFIA CITY COURT

HOWEVER, IN ORDER TO LOSE A PROPERTY WHICH I PAYED IN 1998. Judge DIMCHEVA deliberately did not send the case to the Sofia City Court under the jurisdiction of the Sofia City Court, but TERMINATED THE CASE.

4.12 / . FOURTH MAFIA PRACTICE. THE EXTENDED TERM WITH WHICH IT WAS REQUESTED WAS NOT INFORMED IN ANY WAY. SO THE PRACTICE IS INDISPUTABLE. WITHOUT NOTIFICATION for extension of the term, Judge VESELINA DIMCHEVA FROM ZLATOGRAD TERMINATES THE CASE.

5 / . NOT TO RESPECT THE LAW as a judge MEANS THAT THIS IS THE TOP OF FASCISM IN THIS COUNTRY.

In Civil Case 2794/2014 - 26th Panel of the SCC, Judge Hristo KRASTEV KRACHUNOV issued Order № 556550 of 7 December 2018, returning my claim

Instead of sending the case under the jurisdiction of the SOFIA CITY COURT, BECAUSE THE CASE IS NO LONGER HIS JURISDICTION, IT TERMINATES THE CASE AND RETURNS THE CLAIM, WHATEVER IT IS.

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5 / . TERMINATION OF CASES. DESPITE SATISFACTION OF INSTRUCTIONS FROM A JUDGE, THE JUDGE AS ALEXANDER EMILOV ANGELOV, HRISTO KRACHUNOV, VLADIMIR VALKOV, RAINA MARTINOVA, LYUBKA GOLAKATOVA. The termination was appealed, but the JUDGES FROM THE SOFIA COURT OF APPEAL and respectively from the SUPREME COURT OF CASSATION CONFIRMED THE TERMINATION OF THE CASES €

This is how cases against MAFIA PEOPLE, mafia companies,

LOSSES FOR 25 MILLION EUROS ..

6/. Termination of CASES AGAINST MAFIA COMPANIES - TELEVISIONS, NEWSPAPERS, JOURNALISTS WHO DISTRIBUTED DEFAMATION, LIES, ACCUSED NATURAL PERSONS,

8/. THE MAFIOTIZATION IN THE SUPREME ADMINISTRATIVE COURT AND THE SUPREME COURT OF CASSATION IN FAVOR OF THE COUNCIL OF MINISTERS, MANAGERS OF MINISTERS. CRIMINAL LAWLESSNESS, DOUBLE STANDARDS, ORDERS, REPRESSIONS?!?!)

ORDERS FULFILLED BY SUPREME CASSATION AND SUPREME ADMINISTRATIVE AND OTHER JUDGES IN FAVOR AND BY ORDER OF THE EXECUTIVE AUTHORITY - Council of Ministers, Ministries and others

1 /. Judges of the Supreme Court of Cassation - Tanya Raykovska, Daria Prodanova, Totka Kalcheva, Nikola Hitrov, Eleonora Chanacheva, Emil Markov, judges of Glozhenska, Bozhikov, Spasov of the Court of Appeal Plovdiv grossly violate Bulgarian and European laws deliberate violation of a mandatory directive6 / EU of the European Union and the European Commission from 01.01.2010 according to which from 01.01.2011 the state company Bulgarian Posts EAD does not have a monopoly on its activity, and the same monopoly has been revoked as of January 1, 2011. and in reality they caused losses in a particularly large amount, fulfilling an order of the executive power and did not declare the state company "Bulgarian Posts" bankrupt. LOSSES OVER \$ 250 billion.

The same judges allow themselves under item 519/2012 of the Supreme Court of Cassation, under case file 798/2011, case file 689/2011, of the Court of Appeal Plovdiv, under case file 3765/2013 to confirm the termination of the bankruptcy case of the company "Bulgarian Posts" EAD for its liability in the amount of over 50 000 000 000 / fifty billion / euros, and actually in addition to violating the laws and caused the above huge loss , DONE ONLY IN FAVOR OF THE STATE MAFIA, IN FAVOR OF CRIMINAL ACTIONS OF MINISTERS, EXECUTIVE DIRECTORS OF THE STATE FIRM "FIRM".

EUROPEAN DIRECTIVE 2008/6 // EU IS MANDATORY TO ALL BULGARIAN JUDGES.

2. /. The judges of the Supreme Administrative Court under Adm. Case 4696/2014 instead of terminating an illegal concession granted on 04.06.2010. by the Council of Ministers with Prime Minister BOYKO BORISOV - PRIVATE LAND of the concessionaire "Celsian" WROTE that THIS LAND is MUNICIPAL PROPERTY, although it has been proven that the land from 2008. is PRIVATE PROPERTY owned by the companies "Goldman" Ltd. and "Goldberg Group" Ltd. Losses of \$ 5 billion - failed investments.

4. /. The judges of the Supreme Administrative Court and the Administrative Court of Sofia City support the mafia of Sofia Municipality and the municipalities of Sofia Municipality in the definitions - ARBITRARELY - NOT BY LAW of the tax assessments of real estate. Losses of over 120 million euros.

5. /. Judges of the Supreme Administrative Court and the Sofia City Administrative Court support the lawlessness of the Minister of Justice TSETSKA TSACHEVA who refuses to comply with the law and issue an order to check the actions of PEA Georgi Dichev in connection with returning money to a buyer over BGN 700,000 to the buyer. and practically ensured that the buyer would acquire only for his claim of 150,000 properties for millions of levs ..- without money ..

6. /. The judges of the Supreme Administrative Court and the Administrative Court of Sofia City support the lawlessness of the Minister of Justice TSETSKA TSACHEVA, who refuses to comply with the law and to issue an order to check the fate of PEA Stoyan Yakimov.

7 /. Judges Galina Mateyska, Todor Petrov and Svetoslav Slavov of the Supreme Administrative Court legalized under Admdebo 4696/2014 - 4th Division of the Supreme Administrative Court a crime of the Council of Ministers with Prime Minister BOYKO METODIEV BORISOV and respectively Decision of MINISTERS. with Prime Minister Sergey Stanishev and subsequently with Decision № 69 of 15.02.2010 with Prime Minister Boyko Borisov decided to conclude an ILLEGAL CONCESSION with the company "CELSIAN" on privately owned properties for 35 years, as the Council of Ministers has determined and given LAND - additional to

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a concession area of 2,928.5 in the amount of an additional area of 9,084 decares PRIVATE PROPERTY, WITH THE PURPOSE PURPOSE TO BE ROBBED THIS PROPERTY, for which the mayor of Sofia Municipality Boybo Borisov, when he is poor

9 /. ILLEGALITY OF THE ACTS AND ACTIONS OF THE DEPUTY CHAIRMAN OF THE SUPREME COURT OF CASSATION KRASIMIR VLAHOV - now a constitutional judge

The Deputy Chairman of the Supreme Court of Cassation KRASIMIR VLAHOV, in violation of the law, himself appoints judges to hear cases without using the electronic system for random selection. He has been doing it for more than 6 / six / years. There are days when he appoints judges in 30-40 cases in the Supreme Court of Cassation.

The Deputy Chairman of the Supreme Court of Cassation KRASIMIR VLAHOV, in violation of the law, himself appoints judges to hear cases without using the electronic system for random selection. He has been doing it for more than 6 / six / years. There are days when he appoints judges in 30-40 cases in the Supreme Court of Cassation.

According to Resolved is № 46 / 07.08.2019. of the Supreme Judicial Council on an application for access to public information reg. № 46 / 24.-07.2019 it is allowed to provide full access, CONFIRMING that Judge Krassimir Vlahov did not participate in the competition for the promotion of judges to the Supreme Court of Cassation. He was appointed by a decision of the SJC under protocol № 14 / 05.04.2012. for "Deputy Administrative Head - Deputy President" of the Supreme Court of Cassation on the proposal of the President of the Court.

The procedure for election of the Chairman of the SAC, in which Georgi Kolev participated, was terminated by a decision under Protocol № 38 of 21.10.2010. of the SJC, and Georgi Kolev was elected chairman of the SJC by a decision of the SJC under protocol № 42 of 15.11.2010. He was appointed to the position by Decree № 311 / 17.11.2010.

le the above proves that ALL JUDICIAL ACTS SIGNED by Judge Krassimir Vlahov are null and void - ie. since 2012 because he has never and in no way participated in a competition for a judge in the Supreme Court of Cassation and has not been elected in such a competition for a judge of the Supreme Court of Cassation.

Although in the distant 2012-2013 the chairman of the Supreme Court of Cassation Prof. LAZAR GRUEV was informed about the above, he did not take any action.

Although the SUPREME JUDICIAL COUNCIL and all its members Georgi CHOLAKOV, Atanaska Disheva, Boryana Dimitrova, Krassimi Shekerdzhiev, Olga Karelska, SEVDALIN MAVROV, Tsvetanka Pashkunova, Boyan Magdalinchev, Boyan Kovacheva, Verokov, Verova, Vero Novava, Verokov, Vero Novava, Verokov FOR THIS LAWLESSNESS of the then judge KRASIMIR VLAHOV - they did not take any action for his dismissal. He is ALREADY A CONSTITUTIONAL JUDGE, and even after President RUMEN RADEV was informed of these irregularities by the judge, he confirmed him as a constitutional judge.

Although Chief Prosecutor SOTIR TSATSAROV and Chief Prosecutor IVAN GESHEV were notified of these illegal actions by Krassimir VLAHOV, there were no actions by the prosecution.

2 /. On the other hand, Krassimir Vlahov appoints judges with his Orders on specific cases, as they should be decided IN FAVOR OF THE MAFIA and CAUSE LOSS FOR HUNDREDS OF MILLIONS OF EUROS.

Judge Krassimir Vlahov in the distant 2013 on chgrd. 1252/13 1253/13 and 1254/13 appoints EXACTLY IDENTIFIED THREE SAME JUDGES in three different cases and private appeals in pending cases for a claim of 12 million VERO € against Sofia Municipality with Mayor BOYKO BORISOV and F.

On the other hand, Judge KRASIMIR VLAHOD with an Order from October 2017. Appoints dozens of judges in specific cases without using the random selection system.

For the closed court hearing on 30.10.2017 Judge Genika Mihaylova on

With judges Maria Ivanova and Jiva Dekova

Judge Veska Raycheva in civil case 950/2017

To Genoveva Nikolaeva on 1326/2017 with Maria Ivanova and Jiva Dekova

Judge Maya Ruseva on 1810/2017 s

At the court hearing on 07.11.2017.

For the open court hearing on 27.11.2017 at the first court hearing on December 5, 2017.

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3 /. In reality, the Supreme Court of Cassation legitimizes the thefts of properties of companies from the MAFIA, the thefts of properties in favor of third parties, confirms thefts of properties committed by SAS judges in favor of third parties, legalizes REPRESSIONS - REPRESSIONS of RAINA Martinova confirmed by the judges of the Supreme Court of Cassation, cited above.

In reality, the Supreme Court of Cassation legitimizes the TERMINATION OF ALL CASES FOR THE THEFUL AN EMIL KYULEV of properties of the heirs of insurance companies - PROPERTIES FOR OVER 600 MILLION EUROS - apparently in the order of the mafia.

In reality, the Supreme Court of Cassation legitimizes all terminations of cases ordered by the MAFIA and terminated at the first hearing in the SCC, SCC, KOS, VOS, MES, Vidin District Court and other courts.

4 /.- The signals to the prosecutor's office - Chief Prosecutor SOTIR TSATSAROV - without any action

To the Prosecutor's Office the Chief Prosecutor 52457 dated 30.10.2017

5 /. The signals to the Minister of Justice - MINISTER TSETSKA TSACHEVA without any actions

To the Minister of Justice 94-M-456 dated 31.10.2017

10 /. MAFIOTIZATION OF THE COURT - LEGALIZATION BY JUDGES THEFT OF PRIVATE PROPERTY IN FAVOR OF CAPITAL MUNICIPALITY with Mayor FANDAKOVA

1 /. DECISION from 02.09.2019 of the judges Vladimir Valkov, Maria Boycheva and Jr. Judge Desislava from the Sofia City Court under gr.d. 10481/2009

In violation of the law and the evidence, the judges do not cite, respect, or even mention the following facts and evidence in the case:

Decision № 178 ogt 13.01.2004 of the Supreme Administrative Court under Adm. Case 5159/2003, which entered into force, by which the SAC explicitly ruled that the CITY MUNICIPALITY is not the OWNER of the entire property at 1 Positano Str., Sofia - a three-storey building, shops and land. Explicitly in the reasons of the Supreme Administrative Court is the fact that the property belongs to the heirs of the owners of the insurance company, owner of the property before 1944.

Nevertheless, a decision came into force on 19.02.2004. Judges VLADIMIR VALKOV, DESISLAVA YORDANOVA and MARIYA BOYCHEVA ruled with their decision that THE PROPERTY IS OWNED BY A CAPITAL MUNICIPALITY, which is in fact a legalization of theft of a private property. we are the heirs of the owners of the property at 1 Positano Street - the ideal center of Sofia.

Judges VALKOV, YORDANOVA and BOYCHEVA confused the provisions of the Commercial Law of 1897. for the formation of a joint-stock company, how did judges VALKOV, YORDANOVA and BOYCHEVA confuse the LAW ON COOPERATIVE ASSOCIATIONS OF FEBRUARY 17, 1907? WHEN THEY DON'T RESPECT THAT SUCH ASSOCIATIONS ARE FORMED WITH CAPITAL AND SHARES ??

Judges VALKOV, YORDANOVA and BOYCHEVA mixed the current Law on Cooperatives, where there are no shares, with the LAW ON COOPERATIVE ASSOCIATIONS of February 17, 1907. ?!?!

Judges VALKOV, YORDANOVA and BOYCHEVA mixed SHAREHOLDER RIGHTS - RIGHTS OF OWNERS WITH SHARES according to the Commercial Law of 1897, and the COOPERATIVE ASSOCIATIONS ACT of 1907. with the Ordinance on the Law on Mutual Insurance Associations of 1936. Where it is SPECIFIED INSURANCE ACTIVITY and not OWNERSHIP of companies and joint stock companies. ?!?!

Judges VALKOV YORDANOVA and BOYCHEVA CONSCIOUSLY CONFUSED AND CONSCIOUSLY DISCONTINUED THE SHARE OWNERSHIP OF OUR INHERITANCE in the company Musala - Land, transformed into the last company, as evidenced by Protocol 7 of the Extraordinary attached to the present case FROM WHICH IT IS SHOWN THAT THE INHERITANCE HAS SHARES OF 1464 shares / one thousand four hundred and sixty-four8 / of a total of 5646 / five thousand six hundred and forty-six / shares or this makes 25,929 PERCENT / twenty-five percent of SHARES OF THE CAPITAL OF THE COMPANY?!?!

Judges VALKOV YORDANOVA and BOYCHEVA do not even mention this indisputable PROVEN FACT.

There is a clear and proven art. 282 of the Criminal Code.

THE INACTION OF THE PROSECUTORS OF THE CHIEF PROSECUTOR SOTIR TSATSAROV AND IVAN GESHEV and of the SPECIALIZED PROSECUTORS to initiate a criminal case against the JUDGES WHO VIOLATED THE LAW ON THE LAW ON

2 /. Another DECISION of the judges Milen Vassilev, Alexander E. Angelov and Genika A. Mihailova from 2011 which legalizes the theft of inherited property from - land by the heirs in FAVOR OF THE CAPITAL MUNICIPALITY Decision from 07.02.2013.

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confirmed by Judges Janin Sidareva, Margarita Sokolova and Galabina Gencheva from the Supreme Court of Cassation on 22.10.2013.

ANOTHER LOSS for the heirs

Restitution of ownership over 50/100 id. Parts of a property in the center of Sofia is sought, and according to the decision of the above mentioned judges the land belongs to the apartments sold in the 70s of the last century, and we must explicitly note that then no state land was actually sold. In fact, all apartments sold by the Municipal Councils and services to citizens have only the right to build. According to this decision, virtually all owners of prefabricated homes throughout Sofia must be owners of the land below them, which is not the case.

And on the condition that Judge Alexander Angelov had reprimanded himself in 2011 in cases led by MG cases - ie. the same scheme applies.

11 / . SUPPORT FROM THE CHAIRMEN OF THE Sofia City Court - ALEKSEY TRIFONOV, the former chairman of the SCC KALOYAN TOPALOV, Popkoleva, the chairman of the Sofia Appellate Court - Judge DANIELA DONCHEVA, the chairman of the SCC - the former chairman of the Supreme Court of Cassation performed by their wards

THEIR INACTION REGARDING THEIR OBLIGATIONS UNDER ART. 312 of the JSA to request disciplinary punishment and dismissal of guilty judges from their courts

The Presidents of the Sofia City Court - Judge Alexei Trifonov and the former Presidents Kaloyan Topalov, Popkoleva, of the Sofia Court of Appeal - Judge Daniela Doncheva and the Supreme Court of Cassation and the President of the Supreme Court of Cassation Prof. Lazar Gruev have been repeatedly notified of illegal actions. their judges, as a small part of the cited examples of all judges cited so far in this article, by their courts and they have been asked to fulfill their obligations under Art. 312 of the Judiciary Act - WITHOUT RESULT. NOTHING!?!?! In reality, they do not comply with the laws of this country, to demand disciplinary punishment for the lawlessness of their subordinate judges.

The mafiotization in the Sofia Court of Appeal chaired by DANIELA DONCHEVA - in fulfillment of MAFIA ORDERS - THE MAFIA LEGALISTER-

Mafiaism in the Sofia Court of Appeal - although the judges of the Sofia Court of Appeal recused themselves in hundreds of cases of certain citizens in the lower instance - the Sofia Radical Court, when they were judges of the lower instance, INSTEAD OF GIVING A COURT the execution of the order - the termination of the cases in the Sofia City Court, Kyustendil District Court, Vratsa District Court, and other courts.

Such are the judges - Albena Alexandrova, Sonya Naidenova, Stella Katsarova, Juliana Petkova, Denitsa Tsvetkova, Rozinela Yancheva, Ralitsa D., Elena Mavrova, Dragomir Dragnev - already in the Supreme Court of Cassation, Kodzhabasheva, Hrispime Magardichyan, VERIKE VANLI VASI , Maria Yanachkova, Zornitsa Ezekieva, HAYDUKOVA, Tsvetomira Kordolovska, Lyubomir Vassilev, Krassimir Mashev, Olga Kadankova, Milen Vassilev, Anelia Markova, Elizabet Petrova, NIKOLAY DIMOV, Zlatka Choleva, Velina Peichivava, Epa Andareva Tane Toneva , Nina Stoycheva, DANIELA DONCHEVA, Krassimir Mazgalov, ASEN VODENICHAROV - who terminated a case for 121 million euros without a single court hearing, Miroslava Katsarska, Petar Teodosiev, Jacqueline Komitova, Nikola CHOMPALOV and dozens of others.

The Sofia Court of Appeals, headed by Judge DANIELA DONCHEVA, is the LEGALIZER OF THE MAFIA.

Any lawlessness in Sofia City Court judges Albena BOTEVA, Vladimir Valkov Elitsa Yordanova, Raina MARTINOVA, LYUBKA GOLAKOVA, SVILEN STANCHEV UZAKONYAVA- be confirmed by judges from the Sofia Appellate Court, legalizing IS THEFT OF COMPANIES OF EQUIPMENT FOR MILLIONS, legalization IS THEFT OF PROPERTIES.

The scheme applied by the Sofia Court of Appeals, headed by Judge DANIELA DONCHEVA - SAS, is sent to the jurisdiction of defendants whose addresses are in the CITY OF SOFIA - of the Kyustendil District Court, or the Kyustendil District Court, CASES - TERMINATE CASES. CASES FOR THEFT OF SLOT MACHINES AND BINGO EQUIPMENT FOR TENS MILLION EUROS BY THE JUDGE of the Sofia City Court Yordanka BORISOVA MOLLOVA and HRISTO MOLLOV.

The inaction and lawlessness of ALEKSEY TRIFONOV the genal manager of the Sofia City Court – the biggest court in Bulgaria

In Kyustendil, CASES FOR PROPERTIES WORTH HUNDRED MILLIONS OF EUROS, stolen by EMIL KYULEV from the heirs of the owners of the insurance companies, have been TERMINATED.

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In the Kyustendil District Court, cases with paid state fees for the property at 6 TSAR OSVOBODITEL Blvd.

The Kyustendil District Court has terminated a case for the building in the center of Sofia on Sveta Sofia Street owned by the heirs of an insurance company, ROBBED BY DONEV'S COMPANY - a four-storey building with the right to build for 9 FLOORS.

The Kyustendil District Court has terminated cases against the Ministry of Interior, the National Revenue Agency and OTHER INSTITUTIONS.

In general, it is an interesting fact that all judges of the KYUSTENDIL DISTRICT COURT ARE MULTIPLE AND ALL HAVE EVEN 2-3 PROPERTIES IN THE CITY OF SOFIA in the Supreme Court of Cassation.

This is how the mafia works in the Sofia Court of Appeal.

The SAS Mafia - WHEN A PERFORMANCE SHEET MUST BE ISSUED All SAS judges are reprimanded, however, when a decision has to be made - to cause a loss of property worth 500 million euros - the same judges do not reject each other but rule - losses - example Judge NELI KUTSKOVA.

This is the mafia of the Sofia Court of Appeals, LEADED BY JUDGE Daniela Doncheva.

The same judge DANIELA DONCHEVA, who terminated the insolvency case of Bulgarian Posts EAD because he was allegedly a monopolist, and since 2010. According to the DIRECTIVE AND REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION, "Bulgarian Posts" is NOT a monopolist - and caused a loss of OVER 150 billion US dollars.

At the same time, in cases in the Sofia Court of Appeals, DOCUMENTS, EVIDENCE, REJECTIONS OF JUDGES, rulings of judges disappear.

It is not by chance that in cases in the SAS with presiding judge NELI KUTSKOVA documents, powers of attorney, evidence, even the same "Judge but" monkey "DESPITE THAT SHE GAVE REVIEWS in the cases of this natural person, in cases where pleasure must cause him losses DOES NOT GIVE AWAY and enacts acts by which he caused him huge losses:

- 1 /. IN A CASE for a property purchased by an individual - two-bedroom apartment in the center of Sofia, paid, sold to a third party - DISMISSES THE CLAIM, the construction company since 2017 has not re-registered in the Commercial Register - caused a LOSS OF over 230,000 euros.

2 /. In a case against a debtor, the construction company Vulkanov and Milanov, as in another case with the same defendant, Judge NELI KUTSKOVA recused herself in the case because a company representative went to her husband for a talk, BUT IN THE CASE OF THIS INDIVIDUAL AGAINST THIS CONSTRUCTION COMPANY she does not withdraw and CONFIRMS the replacement of Judge RAINA MARTINOVA on collateral - foreclosure of property against BGN 5,000 paid by the company in a CLAIM FOR OVER BGN 350,000.

LOSS of over BGN 350,000

3 /. In cases in which Judge EVGENI GEORGIEV RELEASES THE KRAMIKOVTSI MAFIA COMPANY with Bankruptcy Trustee BANKOV from paying state fees of millions of Euros IN VIOLATION OF THE LAW, Judge KUTSKOVA VIOLATES AND DISMISSES THE LAW

12/. The inaction and lawlessness of ALEKSEY TRIFONOV the genal manager of the Sofia City Court – the biggest court in Bulgaria

Despite dozens of signals to the Chairman of the Sofia City Court ALEKSEY TRIFONOV iniquity of judges Vladimir Valkov SVILEN STANCHEV Raina MARTINOVA, Elitsa Albena Yordanova BOTEVA, Chairman ALEXEI TRIFONOV not fulfill their statutory want their disciplinary dismissal and punishment.

Moreover, Judges SVILEN STANCHEV and VLADIMIR VALKOV, RAINA MARTINOVA, although they recused themselves in the cases of the same individual, terminated the CASES for 75 million euros, 900,000 euros, 15 million euros.

THE SAME DOES THE CRIMINAL JUDGE IVAN KOEV, who, although he has been reprimanding in criminal cases of a natural person since 2014. the same DECIDES DECISION / DEFINITION 2021. against this natural person, WHICH IS NOT ONLY FOR DISMISSAL BUT ALSO FOR CRIMINAL PROSECUTION.

Moreover, the same criminal judge IVAN KOEV CONFIRMED TERMINATION OF LAWSUITS against judges of the Sofia City Court, the court where he works, which is INADMISSIBLE, who have accused and attributed crimes is what the respective individual is NOT.

UNCONNECTED IS THE FACT THAT THE PRESIDENT OF THE SOFIA CITY COURT WAS BORN IN THE SOVIET UNION AND AT THE AGE OF 16 HE RETURNS TO THE REPUBLIC OF BULGARIA WHICH SUPPORTS AND IMPOSES DUAL CITIZENSHIP, 20 YEARS IN CRIMINAL CASES.

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The lawlessness of Judge KACHERILSKA from the Sofia DISTRICT COURT, which terminated three lawsuits of a natural person against judges who slandered him and attributed to him crimes he did not commit and accused him before a government body, REFUSES TO REMOVE natural person AND EXECUTES CRAZY LAWLESSNESS and disrespect for his human rights. Is THIS IS A PERFORMANCE OF AN ORDER.

DESPITE THE EXPRESSLY FULFILLED ORDER, the chairman of the Sofia City Court ALEKSEY TRIFONOV does not fulfill his obligations to propose Judge KACHERILSKA FOR IMMEDIATE DISMISSAL.

13/. THE REPRESSIONS?!?! CRIMINAL LAWLESSNESS !!!

HOW JUDGES IN BULGARIA TALK TO THE PARTIES IN ONE PROCEEDINGS.

This is a practice for judges Vladimir Valkov, Raina Martinova, Albena Boteva, Elitsa Yordanova, Svilen Stanchev from the Sofia City Court, Nelly Kutzkova from the Sofia Court of Appeal, Judge Zgurov, Judge Vladimir Kanev, the Sofia District Court and dozens more.

Throughout a court hearing, the above judges grin on one side, even after noting that they are judges after all, and their behavior must be different, they continue to grin at the party.

Even the impudence of the judges came to an end, as Judge Vladimir Valkov stated:

"Mr. D... the Bulgarian judges are not responsible for the acts issued by them !!!".

This is a behavior of unscrupulousness, of lawlessness, of a feeling of invulnerability, impunity, a feeling of the LORD towards the citizens who wanted to seek justice.

14 /. THE INACTION OF THE MEMBERS OF THE SUPREME JUDICIAL COUNCIL and the Inspectorate to the Supreme Judicial Council with Chief Inspector Tochkova - the bodies for control of the judiciary, which protect the mafia in court and the lawlessness of judges

Despite the dozens of signals to the members of the Supreme Judicial Council from 2017. by the panel of judges - Georgi Cholakov - Supreme Administrative Court, Atanaska Disheva, Boryana Dimitrova, Krassimir Shekerdzhiiev, Olga Karelska, Sevdalin Mavrov, Tsvetinka Pashkunova, Boan Magdalinchev, Boyan Novanski, Veronika Imova, Daniela Marchevaya and Glavyaya to the SJC Ms. TOCHKOVA for the violations of judges, lawlessness, violation of the laws, non-compliance with the laws, hoaxes with the laws, they do not comply with the laws and allow SUCH LAWLESSNESS, THIS MAFIA AND CORRUPTION IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM.

The same inaction and lawlessness regarding violations, lawlessness, the mafia in the judiciary was carried out by the members of the Supreme Judicial Council for the period 2012 - 2017 Georgi Kolev, Galya Georgieva, Daniela Kostova, Kalin Kalpakchiev, Milka Itova, Julia Kovacheva, Dimitar Uzunov, Galina Karagyova , Karolina Nedelcheva, Maria Kuzmanova, Svetla Petkova, Sonya Naidenova, Sotir Tsatsarov - as Chief Prosecutor.

15 /. THE SIGNALS TO THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE AND THE CHIEF PROSECUTOR IVAN GESHEV and the former Chief Prosecutor SOTIR TSATSAROV and the prosecutors from the specialized prosecutor's office, who have to investigate VIOLATIONS OF THE LAWS BY JUDGES OF JUDGES -

All signals of lawlessness of judges addressed to the former Chief Prosecutor SOTIR TSATSAROV and the current Chief Prosecutor IVAN GESHEV remain without consideration, sink into oblivion, disappear.

The prosecutors from the specialized prosecutor's office who have to deal with corruption and the mafia in the court and respectively the violations of the judges Burgas Court of Appeal, Plovdiv District Court, Plovdiv Court of Appeal, Kyustendil District Court, Kyustendil District Court, Vratsa District Court, and dozens of other courts.

16 /. THE INACTION OF THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION FOR MORE THAN 14 YEARS FOR THE PROVEN CRIMES OF JUDGES

Although the European Commission has been repeatedly informed of the lawlessness, violations of the law, non-compliance with the law, gross violation of the law by the judges in the Bulgarian judiciary, quoted in this article, and CONTINUOUS MONITORING OF OF THE TREATY ON EUROPEAN UNION rudely, stretching an umbrella over the crimes committed by the judges in the Bulgarian court.

THAT IS WHY CLAIMS HAVE BEEN CLAIMED AGAINST THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION AND THE GOVERNMENT OF BULGARIA FOR EURO 325 BILLION DUE TO THE INACTION OF THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

THE RICO Act and THE MAGNITSKY Act - The Only Decision Against the Fight Against the Judges of the Mafia and the MAFIA IN THE COURT in Bulgaria , Supported by the European Commission - Claims to The EC and Bulgaria for 325 Billion Euros From US and other Companies

17/. THE POLITICAL CLASS with prime minister SERGEY STANISHEV and prime minister BOIKO BORISSOV and justice ministers TSETSKA TSACHEVA, DANAIL KIRILOV, EKATERINA ZAHARIEVA, AKHLADOVA PROTECT THE MAFIA in THE JUSTICE SYSTEM IN BULGARIA

Despite the hundreds of proposed changes in the legislation to eliminate this lawlessness of judges, this mafia in court, next to Prime Minister Sergei Stanishev, prime minister Boyko Borisov, ministers Tsetska Tsacheva , minister Danail Kirilov, minister Ekaterina Zaharieva, minister Akhladova, has proven inaction, which proves the support of the mafia in the court of the political class in Bulgaria.

18. CONCLUSION

The described dozens of specific cases of lawlessness, violation of the laws, violation of the laws by the Bulgarian judges - civil and criminal judges, WHICH PROVE THE MAFIA IN THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM IN BULGARIA, which proved how the MAFIA works in the MAFIA in serve the mafia in Bulgaria.

IN GENERAL, WE HAVE PROVED THAT THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM IS A MAFIA AND IS MANAGED BY A MAFIA to satisfy its own corrupt and mafia-targeted goals.

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